

Derivative-Free Sequential Quadratic Programming for Equality-Constrained Stochastic Optimization

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Abstract. We study nonlinear optimization problems with a stochastic objective and deterministic equality constraints, assuming only zeroth-order information is available for both the objective and constraints. We propose a Derivative-Free Stochastic Sequential Quadratic Programming (DF-SSQP) method that uses *simultaneous perturbation stochastic approximation* (SPSA) to estimate gradients and Hessians with a dimension-independent number of function evaluations (as few as eight per step). A key challenge distinguishing DF-SSQP from existing derivative-based SSQP is the random bias led by stochastic zeroth-order approximations. As such, we introduce an online debiasing mechanism based on momentum-style moving-average estimators that aggregate past gradient and Hessian information. Under standard assumptions, we establish global almost-sure convergence and, notably, complement it with a local asymptotic analysis. We show that the rescaled iterate is asymptotically normal with a covariance analogous to the *minimax-optimal* derivative-based counterpart, albeit larger due to the absence of derivative information, reflecting a *statistical-computational trade-off*. Numerical experiments demonstrate both the global convergence and local statistical properties of DF-SSQP.

Key words: Zeroth-order method, Constrained optimization, Sequential quadratic programming, Uncertainty quantification

1. Introduction

We consider solving nonlinear equality-constrained stochastic optimization problems:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^d} f(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathcal{P}}[F(\mathbf{x}; \xi)], \quad \text{s.t.} \quad c(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad (1)$$

where $f : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denotes the stochastic objective function, $F(\cdot; \xi) : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denotes its realization with sample $\xi \sim \mathcal{P}$, and $c : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ denotes the deterministic equality constraints. Problem (1) appears widely in a variety of applications in statistical machine learning and operations research, including constrained maximum likelihood estimation (Dupacova and Wets 1988), multi-stage stochastic optimization (Veliz et al. 2014), reinforcement learning (Achiam et al. 2017), portfolio management (Çakmak and Özekici 2005), and network optimization (Shakkottai and Srikant 2007).

In recent years, designing stochastic sequential quadratic programming (SSQP) methods for solving Problem (1) has attracted growing interest (Berahas et al. 2021b, 2023a, Na et al. 2022, 2023, Curtis et al. 2023, 2024a,b, Fang et al. 2024a, 2025, O’Neill 2024). Although existing literature provides versatile computational methodologies with promising global convergence guarantees and iteration/sample complexities under favorable assumptions, these methods are all derivative-based and require evaluating the gradient (and, in many cases, the Hessian as well) of both the objective and constraints. Such a requirement is restrictive for many applications where gradients are unavailable or too expensive to compute (e.g., black-box simulation models and hyperparameter tuning). This motivates the design of a **Derivative-Free SSQP** method (DF-SSQP) in the present paper.

Throughout the paper, we assume that only zeroth-order information is available for both the stochastic objective and deterministic constraints. This setup situates our work within the broad derivative-free

optimization (DFO) (Conn et al. 2009, Larson et al. 2019, Custódio et al. 2017). As the first attempt to apply DFO to constrained stochastic problems, this paper leverages *Simultaneous Perturbation Stochastic Approximation* (SPSA) technique to randomly estimate the gradients (and Hessians when local convergence is of interest) of the objective and constraints in Problem (1). SPSA and related gradient approximation methods have a long history in optimization and statistics, dating back to Kiefer and Wolfowitz (1952) and continuing through Blum (1954), Koronacki (1975), Spall (1992, 2000), Chen et al. (1999), Hashemi and Pasupathy (2012), Shashaani et al. (2018), Vasquez et al. (2019), Ha and Shashaani (2023). We refer to Chen (1988), Dippon (2003), Broadie et al. (2011), Berahas et al. (2019a,b, 2021a), Rásonyi and Tikosi (2022), Chen et al. (2024), Du-Yi et al. (2024), Llamas et al. (2024), Bollapragada et al. (2025) and references therein for a broader literature review and empirical investigations in DFO. At each iteration \mathbf{x}_k , we generate a sample $\xi_k \sim \mathcal{P}$ and a random direction $\Delta_k \in \mathbb{R}^d$, and approximate the objective gradient $\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and the constraint Jacobian $\nabla c(\mathbf{x}_k) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}$ as

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) &= \frac{F(\mathbf{x}_k + b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k) - F(\mathbf{x}_k - b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k)}{2b_k} \Delta_k^{-1}, \\ \widehat{\nabla} c(\mathbf{x}_k) &= \frac{c(\mathbf{x}_k + b_k \Delta_k) - c(\mathbf{x}_k - b_k \Delta_k)}{2b_k} \Delta_k^{-T},\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where $b_k > 0$ is a deterministic sequence going to zero as $k \rightarrow \infty$, and $\Delta_k^{-1} := (\frac{1}{\Delta_k^1}, \dots, \frac{1}{\Delta_k^d}) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is entry-wise reciprocal of $\Delta_k = (\Delta_k^1, \dots, \Delta_k^d)$. Numerous studies have shown that randomized approximations such as SPSA in (2) dramatically reduce the number of function evaluations. For a d -dimensional problem, the number of function evaluations of SPSA is only $1/d$ of that required by deterministic finite differences, making it *dimension-independent*.

Applying SPSA (and broad DFO techniques) to SSQP introduces a key challenge: all gradient and Hessian estimates of the objective and constraints are subject to intricate random bias brought by both random direction Δ_k and finite-difference approximation. In contrast, existing derivative-based line-search or trust-region SSQP all rely on *unbiased* gradient and Hessian estimates. To address this challenge, we propose an online debiasing technique based on momentum-style estimators that properly aggregate all past gradient and Hessian information via a low-memory moving-average scheme. Under standard assumptions, we demonstrate that the KKT residual of the iteration sequence \mathbf{x}_k converges to zero almost surely from any initialization. More significantly, we complement the global analysis with new local convergence guarantees by showing that the rescaled iterates exhibit asymptotic normality:

$$1/\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}^*, \lambda_k - \lambda^*) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \Sigma^*),$$

where $\bar{\alpha}_k$ is the adaptive random stepsize and the limiting covariance matrix Σ^* is given by a sandwich form (see Section 4 for details):

$$\Sigma^* := (\nabla^2 \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*))^{-1} \text{diag} \left(\mathbb{E} \left[\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \Delta \Delta^{-T} \right], \mathbf{0} \right) (\nabla^2 \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*))^{-1}. \quad (3)$$

Here, $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \lambda) = f(\mathbf{x}) + c^T(\mathbf{x})\lambda$ denotes the Lagrangian function, and the expectation is taken over the randomness in Δ . We show that the covariance Σ^* in (3) closely resembles the *minimax optimal covariance* achieved by derivative-based methods (Duchi and Ruan 2021, Davis et al. 2024, Na and Mahoney 2025, Du et al. 2025):

$$\Sigma_{op}^* = (\nabla^2 \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*))^{-1} \text{diag} (\text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)), \mathbf{0}) (\nabla^2 \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*))^{-1}. \quad (4)$$

However, $\Sigma^\star \succeq \Sigma_{op}^\star$ due to the absence of gradient computations. Furthermore, we show that

$$\|\Sigma^\star - \Sigma_{op}^\star\| \asymp O(d),$$

where \asymp denotes the precise order in the sense that $d/C \leq \|\Sigma^\star - \Sigma_{op}^\star\| \leq Cd$ for some constant C . To our knowledge, the above result provides the first local asymptotic analysis of DFO methods under constrained settings, highlighting an interesting *trade-off between statistical and computational efficiency*. Derivative-based SSQP prioritizes statistical efficiency at expense of computational efficiency, while DF-SSQP prioritizes computational efficiency but inevitably sacrifices certain statistical efficiency. In particular, DF-SSQP requires only a dimension-independent number of function evaluations to approximate derivatives, while its statistical efficiency gap sharply grows linearly in the dimension d .

• **Notation.** We use $\|\cdot\|$ to denote the ℓ_2 -norm for vectors and the operator norm for matrices. We let I denote the identity matrix and $\mathbf{0}$ denote the zero vector or matrix. Their dimensions are clear from the context. For the constraint $c : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$, we define $G(\mathbf{x}) := \nabla c(\mathbf{x}) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}$ as its Jacobian matrix. For $1 \leq j \leq m$, we use the superscript $c^j(\mathbf{x})$ to denote the j -th component of $c(\mathbf{x})$; and for any iteration index k , we let $c_k = c(\mathbf{x}_k)$ and $G_k = G(\mathbf{x}_k) = \nabla c(\mathbf{x}_k)$ (similarly, $\nabla \mathcal{L}_k = \nabla \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_k, \lambda_k)$, etc.). We also use $O(\cdot)$ to denote the big- O notation in the usual sense; that is, $a_k = O(b_k)$ if $|a_k|/|b_k|$ is bounded.

2. Derivative-Free Stochastic Sequential Quadratic Programming

In this section, we propose the DF-SSQP method, which is summarized in Algorithm 1. In Section 2.1, we introduce the gradient and Hessian estimates of the objective and constraints along with our debiasing, momentum-style step. In Section 2.2, we provide a detailed explanation of each step of DF-SSQP.

2.1. Debaised derivatives via averaging

Given the k -th iterate \mathbf{x}_k , we draw a sample $\xi_k \sim \mathcal{P}$ and two independent random directions $\Delta_k, \tilde{\Delta}_k \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

• **Gradient Estimate.** Let $\{b_k\}$ and $\{\beta_k\}$ be predefined positive sequences. As introduced in Section 1, we approximate the objective gradient $\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ and constraint Jacobian $G_k = \nabla c(\mathbf{x}_k) \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}$ by $\tilde{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k)$ and $\tilde{\nabla} c(\mathbf{x}_k)$ as defined in (2). We further perform a debiasing momentum-style step via

$$\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k = (1 - \beta_k)\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{k-1} + \beta_k \tilde{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{G}_k = (1 - \beta_k)\bar{G}_{k-1} + \beta_k \tilde{\nabla} c(\mathbf{x}_k). \quad (5)$$

This moving averaging technique is essential to our method. In Lemma 1, we show the almost-sure convergence of $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k$ to ∇f_k and \bar{G}_k to G_k , which cannot hold for $\tilde{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k)$ and $\tilde{\nabla} c(\mathbf{x}_k)$.

• **Hessian Estimate.** The Hessian estimate is only necessary when local convergence is of interest (cf. Section 4). Let $\{\tilde{b}_k\}$ be another predefined positive sequence. We first compute the gradient estimates:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k) &= \frac{F(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k + \tilde{b}_k \tilde{\Delta}_k; \xi_k) - F(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k)}{\tilde{b}_k} \tilde{\Delta}_k^{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^d, \\ \tilde{\nabla} c(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k) &= \frac{c(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k + \tilde{b}_k \tilde{\Delta}_k) - c(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k)}{\tilde{b}_k} \tilde{\Delta}_k^{-T} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Here, we use $\tilde{\nabla}$ to distinguish it from $\tilde{\nabla}$, where $\tilde{\nabla}$ employs a one-sided finite-difference approximation. This reduces the number of function evaluations as $F(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k)$ and $c(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k)$ are already computed from the gradient estimation. With the above estimates, we then estimate the Hessians as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\delta \tilde{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k)}{2b_k} \Delta_k^{-T} + \Delta_k^{-1} \frac{\{\delta \tilde{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k)\}^T}{2b_k} \right], \\ \tilde{\nabla}^2 c^j(\mathbf{x}_k) &= \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\delta \tilde{\nabla} c^j(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k)}{2b_k} \Delta_k^{-T} + \Delta_k^{-1} \frac{\{\delta \tilde{\nabla} c^j(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k)\}^T}{2b_k} \right], \quad \text{for } 1 \leq j \leq m, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\widetilde{\nabla}F(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k\Delta_k; \xi_k) &= \widetilde{\nabla}F(\mathbf{x}_k + b_k\Delta_k; \xi_k) - \widetilde{\nabla}F(\mathbf{x}_k - b_k\Delta_k; \xi_k) \in \mathbb{R}^d, \\ \delta\widetilde{\nabla}c^j(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k\Delta_k) &= \widetilde{\nabla}c^j(\mathbf{x}_k + b_k\Delta_k) - \widetilde{\nabla}c^j(\mathbf{x}_k - b_k\Delta_k) \in \mathbb{R}^d,\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

and $\widetilde{\nabla}c^j$ is the transpose of the j -th row of $\widetilde{\nabla}c$. Since the Hessians are not crucial for the convergence of the algorithm, and the debiasing step, if needed, will actually focus on the Lagrangian Hessian, we defer the introduction of Hessian debiasing to the algorithm description in (11) in Section 2.2.

2.2. Algorithm design

Define $\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \lambda) = f(\mathbf{x}) + \lambda^T c(\mathbf{x})$ to be the Lagrange function of (1), where $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^m$ denotes the dual vector. Under proper constraint qualifications, a necessary condition for $(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*)$ being a local solution to (1) is the KKT conditions:

$$\nabla\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*) = \begin{pmatrix} \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*) \\ \nabla_\lambda \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f(\mathbf{x}^*) + G(\mathbf{x}^*)^T \lambda^* \\ c(\mathbf{x}^*) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

Our method can be regarded as an application of Newton's method to the equation $\nabla\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \lambda) = \mathbf{0}$. It requires prespecified positive sequences $\{b_k, \widetilde{b}_k, \alpha_k, \beta_k\}$ and four parameters $\sigma, \varepsilon \in (0, 1), \psi \geq 0, p \geq 1$; and is initialized at $(\mathbf{x}_0, \lambda_0) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^m, \widetilde{\mathbf{g}}_{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^d, \widetilde{G}_{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}, \widetilde{B}_{-1} = I \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$, and $\tau_{-1}, \nu_{-1} > 0$.

Given $(\mathbf{x}_k, \lambda_k)$ at the k -th iteration, we first obtain the gradient and Jacobian estimators $\widetilde{\mathbf{g}}_k$ and \widetilde{G}_k as in (5). To exhibit promising local properties, we also compute the Hessian estimators $\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k)$ and $\{\widehat{\nabla}^2 c^j(\mathbf{x}_k)\}_{j=1}^m$ as in (7). Then, we regularize the Jacobian \widetilde{G}_k as:

$$\widetilde{G}_k = \widetilde{G}_k + \delta_k^G, \quad (10)$$

where $\delta_k^G \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}$ is a regularization matrix such that \widetilde{G}_k has full row rank. With the regularized \widetilde{G}_k , we then compute the following three quantities:

$$\widetilde{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_k = \widetilde{\mathbf{g}}_k + \widetilde{G}_k^T \lambda_k, \quad \widehat{\nabla}_x^2 \mathcal{L}_k = \widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) + \sum_{j=1}^m \lambda_k^j \widehat{\nabla}^2 c^j(\mathbf{x}_k), \quad \widetilde{B}_k = (1 - \beta_k) \widetilde{B}_{k-1} + \beta_k \widehat{\nabla}_x^2 \mathcal{L}_k. \quad (11)$$

Here, $\widetilde{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_k$ and \widetilde{B}_k denote the (debaised) estimates of the Lagrangian gradient and Hessian with respect to \mathbf{x} . We emphasize that we can simply set $\widetilde{B}_k = I$ for the sake of global convergence.

To ensure that the Newton system is well-defined, we also have to regularize the Hessian \widetilde{B}_k as:

$$\widetilde{B}_k = \widetilde{B}_k + \delta_k^B, \quad (12)$$

where $\delta_k^B \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is a regularization matrix such that \widetilde{B}_k is positive definite in the null space $\ker(\widetilde{G}_k)$. With the above derivative approximations, we then solve the following Newton system:

$$\underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \widetilde{B}_k & \widetilde{G}_k^T \\ \widetilde{G}_k & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}}_{\widetilde{W}_k} \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \widetilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k \\ \widetilde{\Delta}\lambda_k \end{pmatrix}}_{\widetilde{\Delta}\mathbf{z}_k} = - \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \widetilde{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_k \\ c_k \end{pmatrix}}_{\widetilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k}, \quad (13)$$

where \widetilde{W}_k and $\widetilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k$ represent the Lagrangian full Hessian and gradient, and $\widetilde{\Delta}\mathbf{z}_k$ is the (exact) Newton direction. We mention that the regularizations in (10) and (12) are important to ensure that \widetilde{W}_k is invertible and the system (13) is well-defined (Nocedal and Wright 2006, Lemma 16.1). We note that regularizing \widetilde{G}_k and \widetilde{B}_k does not introduce additional computational burden compared with standard

SQP methods, whose per-iteration cost is dominated by solving the Newton system (13). In fact, the regularization of \tilde{G}_k and \tilde{B}_k can be embedded within the linear system solver: pivoting strategies and diagonal shifts applied during the LDL^T factorization naturally ensure that \tilde{G}_k is numerically full row-rank and \tilde{B}_k is positive definite on the null space of \tilde{G}_k . Since these operations can be part of the factorization used to compute the Newton step and are applied when necessary, δ_k^G and δ_k^B do not introduce dominant computational overhead.

After obtaining the Newton direction $\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{z}_k = (\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\Delta}\lambda_k)$, we update the primal-dual iterate with a properly selected stepsize $\bar{\alpha}_k$ as:

$$(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}, \lambda_{k+1}) = (\mathbf{x}_k, \lambda_k) + \bar{\alpha}_k(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\Delta}\lambda_k).$$

Similar to Berahas et al. (2021b, 2023a,b) and many references therein, the stepsize $\bar{\alpha}_k$ is selected to achieve a sufficient reduction on an ℓ_2 merit function: $\phi_\tau(\mathbf{x}) = \tau f(\mathbf{x}) + \|c(\mathbf{x})\|$. In particular, given $\tau > 0$, we define its local model at \mathbf{x}_k along the direction $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ as

$$q(\mathbf{d}; \tau, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) = \tau(f_k + \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \mathbf{d} + \frac{1}{2} \max\{\mathbf{d}^T \tilde{B}_k \mathbf{d}, 0\}) + \|c_k + \tilde{G}_k \mathbf{d}\|.$$

When \mathbf{d} satisfies $c_k + \tilde{G}_k \mathbf{d} = \mathbf{0}$ as in (13), the reduction of the local model is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta q(\mathbf{d}; \tau, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) &:= q(\mathbf{0}; \tau, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) - q(\mathbf{d}; \tau, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) \\ &= -\tau(\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \mathbf{d} + 0.5 \max\{\mathbf{d}^T \tilde{B}_k \mathbf{d}, 0\}) + \|c_k\|. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The above formula motivates us to define

$$\tau_k^{\text{trial}} \leftarrow \begin{cases} \infty & \text{if } \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k + \max\{\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k^T \tilde{B}_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k, 0\} \leq 0, \\ \frac{(1-\sigma)\|c_k\|}{\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k + \max\{\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k^T \tilde{B}_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k, 0\}} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

followed by the rule of updating τ_k from τ_{k-1} as

$$\tau_k \leftarrow \begin{cases} \tau_{k-1} & \text{if } \tau_{k-1} \leq \tau_k^{\text{trial}}, \\ (1-\varepsilon)\tau_k^{\text{trial}} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

The above merit parameter rule ensures $\tau_k \leq \tau_k^{\text{trial}}$, so that it immediately follows that

$$\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) \geq \frac{1}{2}\tau_k \max\{\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k^T \tilde{B}_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k, 0\} + \sigma\|c_k\|. \quad (16)$$

Next, we define the updating rule for a ratio parameter ν_k , which builds a connection between the reduction of the local model $q(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k)$ and the step magnitude $\|\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\|^2$. In particular, we let

$$\nu_k \leftarrow \begin{cases} \nu_{k-1} & \text{if } \nu_{k-1} \leq \nu_k^{\text{trial}}, \\ (1-\varepsilon)\nu_k^{\text{trial}} & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad \text{where } \nu_k^{\text{trial}} \leftarrow \frac{\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k)}{\|\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\|^2}. \quad (17)$$

This definition ensures $\nu_k \leq \nu_k^{\text{trial}} = \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) / \|\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\|^2$. In the end, our adaptive random stepsize $\bar{\alpha}_k$ can be selected from any scheme as long as, for a prespecified sequence $\{\alpha_k\}$ and $p \geq 1$,

$$\frac{\nu_k \alpha_k}{\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} \leq \bar{\alpha}_k \leq \frac{\nu_k \alpha_k}{\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p, \quad (18)$$

where $\kappa_{\nabla f}$ and $\kappa_{\nabla c}$ are (estimated) Lipschitz constants of ∇f and ∇c . We summarize the above DF-SSQP method in Algorithm 1 and explain and justify the above stepsize selection rule (18) in Appendix A.

Algorithm 1 Derivative-Free Stochastic SQP (DF-SSQP)

- 1: **Input:** initial iterate $(\mathbf{x}_0, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_0) \in \mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^m$, $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, $\bar{G}_{-1} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}$, $\bar{B}_{-1} = I$, $\tau_{-1}, \nu_{-1} > 0$; positive sequences $\{b_k, \bar{b}_k, \alpha_k, \beta_k\}$, tuning parameters $\sigma, \varepsilon \in (0, 1)$, $\psi \geq 0$, $p \geq 1$.
- 2: **for** $k = 0, 1, \dots$, **do**
- 3: Compute derivative approximations with debiasing steps to obtain $\tilde{G}_k, \tilde{B}_k, \tilde{\nabla}_{\mathbf{x}} \mathcal{L}_k$.
- 4: Solve Newton system (13) to obtain $(\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\Delta} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k)$.
- 5: Compute τ_k as in (15), ν_k as in (17), and then select any random stepsize $\bar{\alpha}_k$ as in (18).
- 6: Update $(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_{k+1}) \leftarrow (\mathbf{x}_k, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k) + \bar{\alpha}_k (\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\Delta} \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k)$.
- 7: **end for**

3. Global Convergence Analysis

In this section, we establish the global almost-sure convergence guarantee for Algorithm 1. We begin by stating assumptions.

ASSUMPTION 1. Let $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ be an open convex set that contains the evaluation sequences $\{\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \boldsymbol{\Delta}_k, \mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \boldsymbol{\Delta}_k + \bar{b}_k \boldsymbol{\Delta}_k\}$. We assume that the objective $f(\mathbf{x})$ and constraints $c(\mathbf{x})$ are thrice differentiable, with bounded first, second, and third derivatives over \mathcal{X} , and $f(\mathbf{x})$ is bounded below by f_{\inf} over \mathcal{X} . Moreover, we assume there exist constants $\kappa_c, \kappa_{1,G}, \kappa_{2,G}, \kappa_{1,\tilde{G}}, \kappa_{2,\tilde{G}} > 0$ such that

$$\|c_k\| \leq \kappa_c, \quad \kappa_{1,G} \cdot I \preceq G_k G_k^T \preceq \kappa_{2,G} \cdot I, \quad \kappa_{1,\tilde{G}} \cdot I \preceq \tilde{G}_k \tilde{G}_k^T \preceq \kappa_{2,\tilde{G}} \cdot I, \quad \forall k \geq 0.$$

Similarly, we assume the regularization δ_k^B in (12) ensures that \tilde{B}_k satisfies $\boldsymbol{\omega}^T \tilde{B}_k \boldsymbol{\omega} \geq \kappa_{1,\tilde{B}} \|\boldsymbol{\omega}\|^2$ for any $\boldsymbol{\omega} \in \{\boldsymbol{\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^d : \tilde{G}_k \boldsymbol{\omega} = \mathbf{0}\}$ and $\|\tilde{B}_k\| \leq \kappa_{2,\tilde{B}}$, for some constants $\kappa_{1,\tilde{B}}, \kappa_{2,\tilde{B}} > 0$.

Assumption 1 is standard in the SSQP and/or derivative-free optimization literature (Berahas et al. 2021b, 2022, Curtis et al. 2024b, Fang et al. 2024a,b, Spall 1992, 2000, 2003). Berahas et al. (2023a) relaxed the full row-rank condition on $G_k = \tilde{G}_k$ to a rank-deficient scenario, although that study employs more sophisticated, derivative-based designs with weaker convergence guarantees. As introduced earlier, the lower-bound condition on \tilde{B}_k in the null space $\ker(\tilde{G}_k)$, together with the full row-rank condition on \tilde{G}_k , ensures the well-definedness of the Newton system (13).

ASSUMPTION 2. For any $\xi \sim \mathcal{P}$ and $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$, we assume $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{x}; \xi) | \mathbf{x}] = f(\mathbf{x})$ and there exists a constant $\Upsilon_m > 0$ such that

$$\text{Bounded } r\text{-moment:} \quad \mathbb{E}[\|\nabla F(\mathbf{x}; \xi) - \nabla f(\mathbf{x})\|^r | \mathbf{x}] \leq \Upsilon_m, \quad (19a)$$

$$\text{Uniformly bounded:} \quad \|\nabla F(\mathbf{x}; \xi) - \nabla f(\mathbf{x})\| \leq \Upsilon_m. \quad (19b)$$

Note that (19b) implies (19a) if we redefine $\Upsilon_m \leftarrow \Upsilon_m^r$ in (19a). In general, we only impose a bounded r -moment condition in (19a) for $\nabla F(\mathbf{x}; \xi)$ when studying the properties of the finite-difference estimate $\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}; \xi)$ in (2) and the debiased estimate $\bar{\mathbf{g}}$ in (5). However, we impose the stronger condition (19b) to establish the stabilization of the merit and ratio parameters (τ_k, ν_k) in Lemma 3, in line with the existing SSQP literature (Berahas et al. 2021b, 2023a, Curtis et al. 2024b, Fang et al. 2024a,b). The boundedness of the gradients is required even for deterministic SQP methods.

The next assumption regards the distribution $\mathcal{P}_{\boldsymbol{\Delta}}$ of the random direction $\boldsymbol{\Delta} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, which is standard in the simultaneous perturbation literature (Spall 1992, 2000, 2003).

ASSUMPTION 3. For $k \geq 0$, we assume $\boldsymbol{\Delta}_k, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\Delta}}_k \sim \mathcal{P}_{\boldsymbol{\Delta}}$ are independent. For any $\boldsymbol{\Delta} \sim \mathcal{P}_{\boldsymbol{\Delta}}$, we assume $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$ has mutually independent entries, each symmetrically distributed about zero with absolute value bounded both from above and below by some constants $\kappa_{\Delta_1}, \kappa_{\Delta_2} > 0$: $\kappa_{\Delta_1} \leq |\Delta^j| \leq \kappa_{\Delta_2}$ for $1 \leq j \leq d$. Here, the superscript j denotes the j -th entry of $\boldsymbol{\Delta}$.

Finally, to ease later presentation, we state several polynomial sequences in the next assumption.

ASSUMPTION 4. We let $\alpha_k = \frac{\iota_1}{(k+1)^{p_1}}$, $\beta_k = \frac{\iota_2}{(k+1)^{p_2}}$, $b_k = \frac{\iota_3}{(k+1)^{p_3}}$, $\tilde{b}_k = \frac{\iota_4}{(k+1)^{p_4}}$, where $\iota_i, p_i > 0$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

In the next subsection, we present preliminary results for momentum-style gradient approximations, which serve as the foundation for later establishing the global convergence of DF-SSQP.

3.1. Guarantees for derivative approximations

Recall that we denote $c_k = c(\mathbf{x}_k)$, $G_k = \nabla c_k = \nabla c(\mathbf{x}_k)$ (similar for ∇f_k , $\nabla^2 f_k$ etc.) for notational simplicity. In the following lemma, we demonstrate the almost-sure convergence of the unconditional bias in the debiased gradient and Hessian approximations computed via moving averages.

LEMMA 1. Under Assumptions 1, 2(19a), 3, 4, we further assume that

$$p_2 \in (0.5, 1], \quad p_1 > p_2, \quad p_3 > 0.5 - 0.5p_2, \quad r \geq 2, \quad r(p_1 - p_2) > 1. \quad (20)$$

Then, $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$ and $\bar{G}_k - G_k \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. Furthermore, if δ_k^G ensures $[\kappa_{1,G}, \kappa_{2,G}] \subseteq (\kappa_{1,\bar{G}}, \kappa_{2,\bar{G}})$, then there exists a (potentially random) $K_G^* < \infty$ such that for all $k \geq K_G^*$, $\tilde{G}_k = \bar{G}_k$.

The next lemma establishes the convergence rate in expectation of $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k$ and \bar{G}_k .

LEMMA 2. Under Assumptions 1, 2(19a), 3, 4, we further assume that

$$p_2 \in (0, 1], \quad p_1 > p_2, \quad r \geq 2, \quad \iota_2 > 0.5 > p_3/\iota_2 \text{ (if } p_2 = 1), \quad p_1 < 1 + \iota_2 \text{ (if } p_2 = 1). \quad (21)$$

Then, we have $\max\{\mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k\|^2], \mathbb{E}[\|\bar{G}_k - G_k\|^2]\} = O(\beta_k + b_k^4 + \alpha_k^2/\beta_k^2)$.

Notably, the result of Lemma 2 can be improved through local analysis, as the direction $\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k$ is merely treated as a term with bounded second moment in the global analysis, while it is shown to vanish in the local analysis. Further details on refining the bound of $\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k$ will be provided in the statistical inference analysis in Section 4. Specifically, see Lemma 7 and Lemma 15 in Appendix G.3 for the improvement of the error term α_k^2/β_k^2 . The conditions of (20) and (21) will be discussed later.

3.2. Global almost-sure convergence

In this subsection, we establish the global almost-sure convergence of DF-SSQP. We first demonstrate, in the next lemma, the stabilization of the merit and ratio parameters (τ_k, ν_k) , which is the only yet crucial result for which we require the boundedness condition (19b).

LEMMA 3. Under Assumptions 1, 2(19b), 3, there exist a (potentially random) $K_{\tau\nu}^* < \infty$ and deterministic constants $\tilde{\tau}, \tilde{\nu} > 0$ such that for all $k \geq K_{\tau\nu}^*$, $\tau_k = \tau_{K_{\tau\nu}^*} \geq \tilde{\tau}$ and $\nu_k = \nu_{K_{\tau\nu}^*} \geq \tilde{\nu}$.

Then, we establish the liminf-type convergence guarantee for the local model reduction (16), which is a key step toward proving the limit-type convergence of Algorithm 1. Let us denote $(\Delta\mathbf{x}_k, \Delta\lambda_k)$ to be the solution of (13), but with $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k$ replaced by ∇f_k and \bar{G}_k replaced by G_k .

LEMMA 4. Under Assumptions 1, 2(19a), 3, 4, we further assume that (i) δ_k^G ensures $[\kappa_{1,G}, \kappa_{2,G}] \subseteq (\kappa_{1,\bar{G}}, \kappa_{2,\bar{G}})$, (ii) p_1, p_2, p_3, r satisfy

$$p_1 \in (0.75, 1], \quad p_2 \in (0.5, 2p_1 - 1), \quad p_3 > 0.5 - 0.5p_2, \quad r(p_1 - p_2) > 1, \quad (22)$$

and (iii) the statement of Lemma 3 holds (ensured by (19b)). Then, we have almost surely

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \bar{B}_k) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\|\Delta\mathbf{x}_k\| + \|c_k\|) = 0.$$

We note that the condition (22) implies both (20) and (21). In particular, since $p_1 \leq 1$, we have $2p_1 - 1 \leq \min\{p_1, 1\}$; thus, (22) implies $p_2 < \min\{p_1, 1\}$ as required by (20) and (21). Furthermore, using $p_2 > 0.5$ and $p_1 \leq 1$, we obtain $r(p_1 - p_2) > 1 \Rightarrow r(p_1 - 0.5) > 1 \Rightarrow r > 2$; thus, the condition $r \geq 2$ in (20) and (21) is also satisfied. In addition, since $p_1 > 0.75$ implies $2p_1 - 1 > 0.5$, we conclude that a feasible region always exists for the parameters $\{p_1, p_2, p_3, r\}$, and this region gets larger as $p_1 \rightarrow 1$.

In the next theorem, we establish the global convergence guarantee of Algorithm 1. Given the primal iterate \mathbf{x}_k generated by Algorithm 1, we define the least squares estimate of the dual solution λ_k^* as $\lambda_k^* = -[\tilde{G}_k \tilde{G}_k^T]^{-1} \tilde{G}_k \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k$ (note that Assumption 1 ensures \tilde{G}_k has full row rank, making λ_k^* well-defined). The next theorem states that the KKT residual of the primal solution \mathbf{x}_k , along with its least-squares dual estimate λ_k^* , converges to zero from any initialization almost surely.

THEOREM 1. *Under the conditions in Lemma 4, $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^*\| + \|c_k\|) = 0$ almost surely.*

We note that our almost-sure convergence result matches those established for both line-search-based SSQP methods (Na et al. 2022, 2023, Curtis et al. 2025) and trust-region-based SSQP methods (Fang et al. 2024a,b). This almost-sure guarantee differs from some prior works that established a liminf-type convergence guarantee for the expected KKT residual (Berahas et al. 2021b, 2023a). Furthermore, all prior works studied derivative-based methods, while our almost-sure result is established for derivative-free SSQP schemes by leveraging the simultaneous perturbation technique.

4. Local Rate and Asymptotic Normality

In this section, we establish the local asymptotic normality guarantee for the iterates $(\mathbf{x}_k, \lambda_k)$ of Algorithm 1. To set the stage of local analysis, we first introduce several (local) assumptions that aim to characterize the algorithm's asymptotic behavior.

ASSUMPTION 5. *We assume $\mathbf{x}_k \rightarrow \mathbf{x}^*$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ to a strict local solution \mathbf{x}^* that satisfies:*

- (a) *Linear Independence Constraint Qualification (LICQ): $G^* = \nabla c(\mathbf{x}^*)$ has full row rank.*
- (b) *Second-Order Sufficient Condition (SOSC): let $\lambda^* \in \mathbb{R}^m$ be the unique Lagrangian multiplier vector satisfying the KKT conditions (9). We assume $\omega^T \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*) \omega \geq \kappa_{1,B} \|\omega\|^2$ for any $\omega \in \{\omega \in \mathbb{R}^d : G^* \omega = \mathbf{0}\}$ and $\|\nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*)\| \leq \kappa_{2,B}$ for some constants $\kappa_{1,B}, \kappa_{2,B} > 0$.*

ASSUMPTION 6. *We assume the Hessian of the sample objective has bounded variance near the solution \mathbf{x}^* . That is, for some $\delta > 0$ and any $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X} \cap \{\mathbf{x} : \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*\| \leq \delta\}$, there exists a constant $\Upsilon_n > 0$ such that $\mathbb{E}[\|\nabla^2 F(\mathbf{x}; \xi) - \nabla^2 f(\mathbf{x})\|^2 | \mathbf{x}] \leq \Upsilon_n$.*

ASSUMPTION 7. *We assume almost surely, $\tau_k = \tau$, $\nu_k = \nu$, $\forall k \geq K_{\tau\nu}^*$, for a (potentially random) index $K_{\tau\nu}^* < \infty$ and two deterministic constants $\tau, \nu > 0$.*

Assumption 5 is standard in the literature for analyzing the local asymptotic behavior of both deterministic and stochastic algorithms for solving constrained nonlinear nonconvex problems (Bertsekas 1982, Nocedal and Wright 2006, Duchi and Ruan 2021, Davis et al. 2024, Na and Mahoney 2025). It is also well known that LICQ and SOSC are necessary conditions even for establishing the asymptotic normality of offline M -estimation (Shapiro et al. 2021, Chapter 5), which ensure the limiting covariance matrix of the M -estimator is well-defined (see (Na and Mahoney 2025, (1.3)) for more details).

We recall that the Hessian approximation is only used to achieve favorable local convergence properties; hence, the bounded variance condition is imposed only locally in Assumption 6. Assumption 7 enforces that the merit and ratio parameters (τ_k, ν_k) stabilize almost surely at some constants (τ, ν) . By Lemma 3, we know the boundedness condition (19b) ensures (τ_k, ν_k) always stabilize, though the limiting values $(\tau_\infty, \nu_\infty) = (\tau_{K_{\tau\nu}^*}, \nu_{K_{\tau\nu}^*})$ may vary in different runs. That said, the assumption of $(\tau_\infty, \nu_\infty) = (\tau, \nu)$ is made solely to simplify the presentation and highlight core challenges. Removing the assumption leads to a limiting mixture Gaussian distribution following the same analysis (cf. Appendix B).

In the following lemma, we demonstrate that the iterates $(\mathbf{x}_k, \lambda_k)$ converge almost surely to the local solution $(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*)$. Note that the conditions on (p_1, p_2, p_3, r) and δ_k^G below are implied by (i.e., weaker than) those required for the global convergence in Theorem 1 (i.e., Lemma 4).

LEMMA 5. Under Assumptions 1, 2(19a), 3, 4, 5, we further assume that (i) δ_k^G ensures $[\kappa_{1,G}, \kappa_{2,G}] \subseteq (\kappa_{1,\bar{G}}, \kappa_{2,\bar{G}})$, and (ii) p_1, p_2, p_3, r satisfy

$$p_1 \in (0.5, 1], \quad p_2 \in (0.5, p_1), \quad p_3 > 0.5 - 0.5p_2, \quad r(p_1 - p_2) > 1. \quad (23)$$

Then, $(\mathbf{x}_k, \lambda_k) \rightarrow (\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*)$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely.

With the above convergence of the iterates, we further establish the convergence of Hessian approximations to complement the convergence of gradient approximations in Lemma 1. Note that Hessian convergence is crucial for local analysis even in deterministic methods to ensure local superlinear rate (so called Dennis-Moré condition (Dennis and Moré 1974)).

LEMMA 6. Under Assumptions 1, 2(19a), 3, 4, 5, 6, we further assume that (i) δ_k^G ensures $[\kappa_{1,G}, \kappa_{2,G}] \subseteq (\kappa_{1,\bar{G}}, \kappa_{2,\bar{G}})$, and (ii) p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, r satisfy

$$p_1 \in (0.5, 1], \quad p_2 \in (0.5, p_1), \quad p_3 > 0.5 - 0.5p_2, \quad p_4 > 0.5p_3, \quad r(p_1 - p_2) > 1. \quad (24)$$

Then, $\bar{B}_k \rightarrow \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^*$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. Furthermore, if δ_k^B ensures $[\kappa_{1,B}, \kappa_{2,B}] \subseteq (\kappa_{1,\bar{B}}, \kappa_{2,\bar{B}})$, then there exists a (potentially random) $K_B^* < \infty$ such that for all $k \geq K_B^*$, $\bar{B}_k = \bar{B}_k$.

We next provide the local convergence rate of the iterate (and the Lagrangian gradient approximation). We use $\mathbf{z}_k = (\mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}^*, \lambda_k - \lambda^*)$ to denote the error of the primal-dual pair and define two matrices:

$$W^* = \nabla^2 \mathcal{L}^* = \begin{pmatrix} \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^* & (G^*)^T \\ G^* & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \Omega^* = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{E}[\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \Delta \Delta^{-T}] & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Our “local neighborhood” is characterized by a stopping time, defined for any $k_0 \geq 0$ and $\epsilon > 0$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{k_0}(\epsilon) = \inf \left\{ k \geq k_0 : \|\mathbf{z}_k\| > \epsilon^2 \text{ OR } \|\bar{W}_k^{-1}\| > \frac{1}{\epsilon} \text{ OR } \|\nabla \mathcal{L}_k - \bar{W}_k \mathbf{z}_k\| > 0.25\epsilon^2 \|\mathbf{z}_k\| \right. \\ \text{OR } \|\nabla \mathcal{L}_k\| > \frac{\|\mathbf{z}_k\|}{\epsilon} \text{ OR } \delta_k^G \neq \mathbf{0} \text{ OR } \delta_k^B \neq \mathbf{0} \text{ OR } \|(\mathbf{x}_k, \lambda_k)\| > \frac{1}{\epsilon} \\ \left. \text{OR } \|\nabla \mathcal{L}_k - W^* \mathbf{z}_k\| > \frac{\|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2}{\epsilon} \text{ OR } \frac{\nu_k}{\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} \neq \frac{\nu}{\tau \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} =: \zeta \right\}. \quad (25) \end{aligned}$$

As expected, we show in Theorem 2 that if ϵ is chosen to be sufficiently small, for each run of the algorithm, there always exists a (potentially random) $\bar{k}_0 > 0$ such that $\tau_{k_0}(\epsilon) = \infty$ for all $k_0 \geq \bar{k}_0$.

LEMMA 7. Under Assumptions 1, 2(19a), 3, 4, and we further assume that

$$p_1 \in (0, 1], \quad p_2 \in (0, p_1), \quad r \geq 2, \quad \zeta_{l_1} > 0.5 \text{ (if } p_1 = 1). \quad (26)$$

Then, for any $\epsilon \in (0, 1 - 0.5/(\zeta_{l_1} \mathbf{1}_{p_1=1}))$, there exists a deterministic integer $\bar{k}_0 > 0$ such that for any $k_0 \geq \bar{k}_0$, there exists a constant $\Upsilon(k_0)$ (depending on k_0) such that

$$\max \left\{ \mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}(\epsilon) > k}], \mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}(\epsilon) > k}] \right\} \leq \Upsilon(k_0) (\beta_k + b_k^4) \quad \text{for any } k \geq k_0.$$

Combining all above lemmas, we are ready to state asymptotic normality behavior of DF-SSQP.

THEOREM 2. Under Assumptions 1, 2(19a), 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, and we further assume that (i) δ_k^G ensures $[\kappa_{1,G}, \kappa_{2,G}] \subseteq (\kappa_{1,\bar{G}}, \kappa_{2,\bar{G}})$ and δ_k^B ensures $[\kappa_{1,B}, \kappa_{2,B}] \subseteq (\kappa_{1,\bar{B}}, \kappa_{2,\bar{B}})$, (ii) p, p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, r satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} p_1 \in (0.5, 1], \quad p_2 \in (0.5, p_1), \quad p_3 > \max\{0.5 - 0.5p_2, 0.25p_1\}, \quad p_4 > 0.5p_3 + 0.25(p_1 - p_2), \\ p > 1.5 - 0.5p_2/p_1, \quad r(p_1 - p_2) > 1, \quad r \geq 3, \quad (27) \end{aligned}$$

and $\zeta_{l_1} > 0.5$ if $p_1 = 1$. Then, we have

$$1/\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}^*, \lambda_k - \lambda^*) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N} \left(\mathbf{0}, \omega \cdot (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1} \right) \quad \text{with} \quad \omega = \begin{cases} \frac{\zeta_{l_1}}{2\zeta_{l_1-1}} & \text{if } p_1 = 1, \\ 0.5 & \text{if } p_1 < 1. \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

The conditions on $\{p, p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4, r\}$ can be easily satisfied. The condition (27) implies (23), (24), (26), thereby ensuring that Lemmas 5, 6, 7 naturally hold. Assuming the gradient $\nabla F(\mathbf{x}; \xi)$ has bounded third moment ($r \geq 3$) is standard in existing literature (Davis et al. 2024, Na and Mahoney 2025). Theorem 2 shows that the rescaled primal-dual error by the random stepsize converges in distribution to Gaussian with mean zero and covariance $\omega \cdot (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1}$. To achieve optimal asymptotic rate (i.e., \sqrt{k} -consistency), we set $p_1 = 1$ (i.e., $O(1/k)$ stepsize) and Theorem 2 implies that

$$\sqrt{k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}^*, \lambda_k - \lambda^*) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N} \left(\mathbf{0}, \frac{(\zeta \iota_1)^2}{2\zeta \iota_1 - 1} \cdot (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1} \right).$$

Thus, the minimum covariance is achieved by setting $\iota_1 := 1/\zeta$ and given by $\Sigma^* := (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1}$. On the other hand, we know from Duchi and Ruan (2021), Davis et al. (2024), Na and Mahoney (2025), Du et al. (2025) that the *minimax optimal covariance* achieved by various derivative-based methods for Problem (1) is given by (recall (4)): $\Sigma_{op}^* := (W^*)^{-1} \text{diag}(\text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)), \mathbf{0}) (W^*)^{-1}$.

The next proposition shows that the derivative-free method, while more computationally efficient, is less statistically efficient than derivative-based methods in the sense that $\Sigma^* \succeq \Sigma_{op}^*$. Moreover, the statistical efficiency gap grows linearly with the dimension d , even though the computational efficiency gap also becomes more and more promising, as the derivative-free method requires only a *dimension-independent* number of function evaluations.

PROPOSITION 1. *Suppose $\Delta \sim \mathcal{P}_\Delta$ satisfies Assumption 3. We have $\Sigma^* \succeq \Sigma_{op}^*$. Furthermore, there exists a constant $Y > 0$ such that $(d-1)/Y \leq \|\Sigma^* - \Sigma_{op}^*\| \leq Y \cdot (d-1)$.*

To conclude this section, we turn our attention to performing online statistical inference in practice. In particular, to conduct hypothesis testing and construct confidence intervals or regions for $(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*)$, a consistent estimator of the limiting covariance in Theorem 2 is required. The next proposition provides a simple plug-in estimator for this purpose.

PROPOSITION 2. *Under the conditions of Theorem 2 and strengthen $r \geq 4$, we define*

$$\Sigma_k = \tilde{W}_k^{-1} \cdot \text{diag} \left(\frac{1}{k+1} \sum_{t=0}^k \left(\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_t; \xi_t) + \widehat{\nabla}^T c(\mathbf{x}_t) \lambda_t \right) \left(\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_t; \xi_t) + \widehat{\nabla}^T c(\mathbf{x}_t) \lambda_t \right)^T, \mathbf{0} \right) \cdot \tilde{W}_k^{-1}$$

and have $\Sigma_k \rightarrow \Sigma^* = (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1}$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely.

We mention that requiring the gradient estimate $\nabla F(\mathbf{x}; \xi)$ to have a bounded fourth moment ($r \geq 4$) is standard for establishing the consistency of the plug-in covariance estimator; see Chen et al. (2020), Davis et al. (2024), Na and Mahoney (2025) and references therein. With Proposition 2, we can now construct the confidence interval of the quantity $(\mathbf{w}_x, \mathbf{w}_\lambda)^T (\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*)$ for any vector $\mathbf{w} = (\mathbf{w}_x, \mathbf{w}_\lambda)$ as:

$$P \left((\mathbf{w}_x, \mathbf{w}_\lambda)^T (\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*) \in \left[(\mathbf{w}_x, \mathbf{w}_\lambda)^T (\mathbf{x}_k, \lambda_k) \pm z_{1-\varphi/2} \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_k \cdot \omega \cdot \mathbf{w}^T \Sigma_k \mathbf{w}} \right] \right) \rightarrow 1 - \varphi \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow \infty.$$

Here, for $\varphi \in (0, 1)$, $z_{1-\varphi/2}$ denotes the $(1 - \varphi/2)$ -quantile of the standard Gaussian distribution.

5. Numerical Experiment

We compare derivative-free methods with derivative-based methods on benchmark constrained nonlinear problems in CUTEst test set (Gould et al. 2014). For both DF-SSQP and derivative-based SSQP, we consider first- and second-order variants. The first-order methods do not estimate $\widehat{\nabla}_x^2 \mathcal{L}_k$ in (11) and instead set it as I . The second-order methods estimate it either via a derivative-free approach in (6)-(8), or obtain it directly from the CUTEst package. Note that no debiasing step is performed for derivative-based methods, i.e., $\beta_k = 1$ in (5) and (11). Detailed experimental setups and extensive results are provided in Appendix C due to the space limit. Here, we report a representative subset of the findings.

Table 1 Comparison of DF-SSQP and DB-SSQP on 4 CUTEst problems under 4 noise variances σ^2 . “/” indicates cases where the iterate error exceeds 1 (the methods may converge to a stationary point different from the one given by the package). Red numbers indicate cases where second-order methods achieve coverage closer to the nominal 95% than first-order methods; blue numbers indicate the converse. Unhighlighted entries are cases where either both first- and second-order methods are near-nominal or both exhibit under- or over-coverage.

Prob	σ^2	Hess	Derivative-Free SSQP				Derivative-Based SSQP				
			Err (10^{-4})	Cov (100%)	Len (10^{-2})	FLOPs	Err (10^{-4})	Cov (100%)	Len (10^{-2})	FLOPs	
HS51	10^{-4}	Id	5.97	99.30	0.08	544.01	0.78	99.60	0.01	552.01	
		Hess	4.12	94.40	0.04	651.01	0.50	96.00	0.00	627.01	
	10^{-2}	Id	62.54	99.40	0.85	544.01	7.00	100.00	0.11	552.01	
		Hess	43.26	92.70	0.36	651.01	5.06	94.70	0.04	627.01	
	10^{-1}	Id	203.20	99.40	2.69	544.01	25.05	99.70	0.35	552.01	
		Hess	137.75	92.20	1.12	651.01	15.61	93.80	0.14	627.01	
	1	Id	691.39	99.60	8.51	544.01	74.99	99.60	1.09	552.01	
		Hess	435.44	93.60	3.54	651.01	45.96	96.90	0.44	627.01	
	HS48	10^{-4}	Id	7.75	99.40	0.11	371.01	0.98	99.70	0.01	378.01
			Hess	5.01	94.70	0.05	454.01	0.64	95.10	0.01	453.01
10^{-2}		Id	82.23	99.30	1.13	371.01	8.68	99.80	0.14	378.01	
		Hess	51.78	94.30	0.48	454.01	6.58	94.10	0.06	453.01	
10^{-1}		Id	253.12	99.20	3.56	371.01	29.26	99.60	0.45	378.01	
		Hess	180.68	91.00	1.48	454.01	19.24	95.50	0.18	453.01	
1		Id	811.96	99.30	11.26	371.01	91.78	99.30	1.42	378.01	
		Hess	577.03	93.90	4.70	454.01	63.69	96.40	0.57	453.01	
BT9		10^{-4}	Id	7.40	98.25	0.15	235.20	1.18	99.25	0.03	240.00
			Hess	5.12	95.50	0.08	289.60	0.80	96.75	0.01	288.01
	10^{-2}	Id	66.83	100.00	1.46	235.20	11.39	99.25	0.26	240.00	
		Hess	7933.70	94.30	0.89	289.60	83.67	95.57	0.13	288.01	
	10^{-1}	Id	236.10	98.50	4.59	235.20	36.02	99.25	0.82	240.00	
		Hess	/	84.81	8.76	289.60	/	88.58	9.57	288.01	
	1	Id	769.04	95.50	14.07	235.20	124.44	99.25	2.60	240.00	
		Hess	/	57.69	57.84	289.60	/	58.04	16.11	288.01	
	BT1	10^{-4}	Id	6.54	93.50	0.15	31.80	1.13	99.00	0.04	33.00
			Hess	6.45	92.50	0.15	42.20	1.10	99.50	0.04	45.00
10^{-2}		Id	64.99	93.00	1.46	31.80	11.95	99.50	0.40	33.00	
		Hess	62.06	93.00	1.47	42.20	10.12	100.00	0.40	45.00	
10^{-1}		Id	217.15	91.50	4.61	31.80	36.24	100.00	1.26	33.00	
		Hess	192.85	92.00	4.64	42.20	32.98	100.00	1.27	45.00	
1		Id	633.13	95.00	14.55	31.80	105.72	100.00	4.10	33.00	
		Hess	610.65	95.00	14.77	42.20	/	100.00	/	45.00	

Specifically, we report the averaged primal-dual iterate error, as well as the averaged coverage rate and length of constructed entrywise 95% confidence intervals over 200 independent runs on 4 CUTEst problems, with 4 different variance levels σ^2 of the Gaussian oracles. We also report the computational flops per step. The results are summarized in Table 1. From the table, we observe that both first- and second-order derivative-based methods (DB-SSQP) generally achieve smaller iterate errors and shorter confidence interval lengths than their derivative-free counterparts (DF-SSQP), with comparable FLOPs, across 4 CUTEst problems (more in Appendix C) and 4 noise levels. This aligns with Proposition 1 and suggests that, whenever available and reliable, derivative information should be used to compute the step direction. That said, in high-noise regimes ($\sigma^2 \in \{0.1, 1\}$), second-order variants may fail to converge or may converge to a stationary point different from the package reference; thus, when second-order estimates are very noisy, incorporating curvature does not necessarily reduce the iterate error.

On the other hand, second-order information significantly improves coverage rate, bringing the empirical rates closer to the nominal rate 95%. In particular, for 3 out of 4 CUTEst problems, we observe many settings in which second-order DF- and DB-SSQP attain coverage rate much nearer nominal 95% level, while corresponding first-order methods suffer obvious under-coverage (below 90%) or over-coverage (near 100%). These observations align with Theorem 2: local asymptotic normality of SSQP highlights the benefits of Hessian information; without it, the normality (28) fails to hold and the limiting covariance is only biasedly estimated, yielding asymptotically mis-calibrated confidence intervals. Notably, on problem BT1, DF-SSQP attains a much better coverage rate than DB-SSQP for both first- and second-order variants; and on the remaining 3 problems (more in Appendix C), DF-SSQP achieves coverage no worse than DB-SSQP. Taken all together, our results indicate that for solution inference, second-order DF-SSQP can be as reliable, and in some cases preferable, as second-order DB-SSQP.

6. Conclusion

We proposed DF-SSQP (Algorithm 1), a derivative-free, fully stochastic method for solving constrained stochastic optimization (1). We established global almost-sure convergence along with a local convergence rate (in expectation). We also proved asymptotic normality with limiting covariance closely resembling the minimax optimal covariance achieved by derivative-based methods. This local result is particularly surprising and significant, not only because it illustrates the trade-off between computational and statistical efficiency, but also because DF-SSQP relies on highly correlated momentum-style gradient estimates; unlike all existing SSQP methods that rely on conditionally independent gradient estimates.

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Appendix

A. Stepsize Selection Justification

The stepsize selection condition (18) follows existing designs of derivative-based SSQP (Berahas et al. 2021b, 2022, Curtis et al. 2024a,b, Na and Mahoney 2025). Essentially, we just set $\bar{\alpha}_k = O(\alpha_k)$, while to introduce the adaptivity into the method, we multiply α_k by the ratio $\nu_k/(\tau_k\kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c})$ and are allowed to increment it with an adaptivity gap $\psi\alpha_k^p$. The adaptivity gap is crucial as it distinguishes our random stepsize schemes from deterministic stepsize schemes ($\psi = 0$). The ratio $\nu_k/(\tau_k\kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c})$, though depends on k , will stabilize when k is sufficiently large under proper assumptions (cf. Lemma 3). The inspiration of the ratio comes from imposing the Armijo condition:

$$\phi_{\tau_k}(\mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k) \leq \phi_{\tau_k}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \gamma \bar{\alpha}_k \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) \quad \text{for } \gamma \in (0, 1). \quad (\text{A.1})$$

In fact, applying the Taylor's expansion and noting that $\kappa_{\nabla f}$ and $\kappa_{\nabla c}$ are Lipschitz constants of ∇f and ∇c , we know for $\bar{\alpha}_k \leq 1$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{\tau_k}(\mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k) &= \tau_k f(\mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k) + \|c(\mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k)\| \\ &\leq \tau_k (f_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \nabla f_k^T \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k) + \|c_k + \bar{\alpha}_k G_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\| + \frac{1}{2} (\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \\ &= \phi_{\tau_k}(\mathbf{x}_k) + \bar{\alpha}_k (\tau_k \nabla f_k^T \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k + \|c_k + G_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\| - \|c_k\|) + \frac{1}{2} (\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \\ &\stackrel{(14)}{\leq} \phi_{\tau_k}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \bar{\alpha}_k \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) + \bar{\alpha}_k \|c_k + G_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\| + \frac{1}{2} (\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\|^2. \end{aligned}$$

Supposing for the moment that $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k \rightarrow \nabla f_k$ and $\tilde{G}_k \rightarrow G_k$ (as proved in Lemma 1), we use $c_k + \tilde{G}_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{0}$ from (13) and have for large enough k that (\lesssim only means for ‘‘intuition’’)

$$\phi_{\tau_k}(\mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k) \lesssim \phi_{\tau_k}(\mathbf{x}_k) - \bar{\alpha}_k \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) + \frac{1}{2} (\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\|^2.$$

Combining the above display with (A.1), we know (A.1) can be satisfied as long as

$$\bar{\alpha}_k \leq \frac{2(1-\gamma)\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k)}{(\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) \|\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k\|^2}.$$

Note that $\nu_k/(\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c})$ is a lower bound of the above right-hand side corresponding to $\gamma = 1/2$.

B. Further Discussions on Stabilization of τ_k, ν_k

Let us discuss Assumption 7 further. We note that, in Algorithm 1, the pair (τ_k, ν_k) only affects the stepsize $\bar{\alpha}_k$ via the factor $\nu_k/(\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c})$ in (18), which, as shown in Theorem 2, may scale the variance of the limiting normal distribution. Since (τ_k, ν_k) are updated multiplicatively by a factor of $1 - \varepsilon$ and are constrained within deterministic lower and upper bounds (cf. Lemma 3), we know the limiting pair $(\tau_\infty, \nu_\infty)$ can only take finitely many discrete values $\{(\tau_{(i)}, \nu_{(i)})\}_{i=1}^N$, forming a discrete distribution. Consequently, the factor $\nu_\infty/(\tau_\infty \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c})$ also follows a discrete distribution with finite support. Thus, by adjusting the filtration from $\mathcal{F}_k = \sigma(\{\xi_i, \Delta_i, \tilde{\Delta}_i\}_{i=0}^k)$ to the trace filtration $\mathcal{F}_k \cap \{(\tau_\infty, \nu_\infty) = (\tau_{(i)}, \nu_{(i)})\}^1$, we can follow the same line of analysis and obtain a limiting mixture normal distribution with N components, where each component has the weight $P(\{(\tau_\infty, \nu_\infty) = (\tau_{(i)}, \nu_{(i)})\})$. Since this extension is tedious and of limited interest and contribution, we leave it for future work.

C. Supplement to Numerical Experiment

In this section, we show supplementary results for numerical experiments in Section 5. We first describe the experimental setup and then present additional global and local results.

• **Experimental setup.** For both derivative-free and derivative-based SSQP, we perform 200 independent runs for each CUTEst problem under each setup and set the total number of iterations to 10^5 . For DF-SSQP, we consider the setting where any order of derivatives of both the objective and constraints are inaccessible, and we apply the SPSA approach to estimate them (see (2), (6)–(8)). The random directions Δ_k and $\tilde{\Delta}_k$ have independent entries drawn from the Rademacher distribution, taking values ± 1 with equal probability. We set the prespecified stepsize, momentum weight, and discretization sequences as $\alpha_k = 1/t^{0.751}$, $\beta_k = 1/t^{0.501}$, $b_k = \tilde{b}_k = 1/t^{0.25}$, $p = 1.5$ according to (22) and

¹The trace filtration contains all randomness from \mathbf{x}_0 to \mathbf{x}_k conditioned on the event $\{(\tau_\infty, \nu_\infty) = (\tau_{(i)}, \nu_{(i)})\}$.

Figure 1 Boxplots over CUTEst problems. Each panel has four different noise levels, and each noise has four different methods.

(27), and designate the first one-fifth of the iterations as the burn-in period. For derivative-based SSQP, we use the same α_k and p . The objective values, gradients, and Hessians (when applicable) are generated by adding Gaussian noise to the true deterministic quantities. Specifically, $F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi) \sim \mathcal{N}(f_k, \sigma^2)$, $\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi) \sim \mathcal{N}(\nabla f_k, \sigma^2(I + \mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^T))$, and $[\nabla^2 F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi)]_{i,j} \sim \mathcal{N}([\nabla^2 f_k]_{i,j}, \sigma^2)$. Here, $\mathbf{1}$ denotes the d -dimensional all-ones vector. We vary the noise variance as $\sigma^2 \in \{10^{-4}, 10^{-2}, 10^{-1}, 1\}$.

C.1. Global convergence

We compare the final KKT residuals, primal-dual iterate errors, computational flops per iteration, and running times of four methods: first- and second-order DF-SSQP and first- and second-order derivative-based SSQP, denoted as DF-Id, DF-Hess, DB-Id, and DB-Hess, respectively. The results are summarized in Figure 1.

Not surprisingly, there are considerable disadvantages to not having derivative information, especially in conjunction with additional random noise in the objective value estimates. Hence, we cannot expect the performance of derivative-free methods to be as competitive as that of derivative-based methods. From Figure 1(a)-(b), we observe that the performance of DF-SSQP degrades, exhibiting higher KKT residuals and iterate errors. This suggests that a near-optimal solution obtained by DF-SSQP is often less accurate than that produced by a derivative-based SSQP method. On the other hand, for both types of methods, we do not observe a significant advantage in approximating second-order information from noisy observations for facilitating global convergence; this, however, becomes clearer in the local study as presented in Section 5 and Appendix C.2. In terms of flops per iteration, all four methods yield comparable results, with first-order methods showing slightly lower costs. This is because all methods have to solve the Newton system (13) at each step, which is the dominant computational cost. In terms of running time, we observe that first-order methods reach stationarity faster than second-order methods, and that derivative-free methods are faster than their derivative-based counterparts.

Table 2 Comparison of DF- and DB-SSQP on 4 CUTEst problems under 4 noise variances σ^2 . See Table 1 for interpretation.

Prob	σ^2	Hess	Derivative-Free SSQP				Derivative-Based SSQP			
			Err (10^{-4})	Cov (100%)	Len (10^{-2})	FLOPs	Err (10^{-4})	Cov (100%)	Len (10^{-2})	FLOPs
MARATOS	10^{-4}	Id	6.54	93.50	0.15	31.80	1.13	94.00	0.03	33.00
		Hess	6.45	92.50	0.15	42.20	1.10	94.50	0.03	45.00
	10^{-2}	Id	64.99	93.00	1.46	31.80	11.95	95.00	0.26	33.00
		Hess	62.06	93.00	1.47	42.20	10.12	97.50	0.26	45.00
	10^{-1}	Id	217.15	91.50	4.61	31.80	36.24	95.00	0.82	33.00
		Hess	192.85	92.00	4.64	42.20	32.98	97.00	0.82	45.00
	1	Id	633.13	95.00	14.55	31.80	105.72	94.50	2.61	33.00
		Hess	610.65	95.00	14.77	42.20	109.65	93.00	2.61	45.00
BYRDSPHR	10^{-4}	Id	8.94	83.50	0.10	137.00	1.11	83.50	0.01	140.00
		Hess	14.39	88.50	0.22	168.80	1.82	92.00	0.03	167.00
	10^{-2}	Id	93.26	80.50	1.03	137.00	10.06	84.50	0.13	140.00
		Hess	126.14	96.25	2.17	168.80	16.76	93.50	0.27	167.00
	10^{-1}	Id	274.76	81.00	3.26	137.00	34.61	79.00	0.41	140.00
		Hess	419.41	92.75	6.85	168.80	49.84	94.75	0.86	167.00
	1	Id	960.05	79.00	10.31	137.00	113.15	84.25	1.30	140.00
		Hess	1478.60	92.00	22.16	168.80	/	95.75	8.40	167.00
BT12	10^{-4}	Id	10.55	87.30	0.08	544.01	1.70	88.40	0.01	552.01
		Hess	11.24	93.00	0.11	651.01	1.85	95.90	0.02	627.01
	10^{-2}	Id	120.78	85.00	0.82	544.01	15.44	93.60	0.13	552.01
		Hess	125.22	90.81	1.13	651.01	500.20	95.05	0.17	627.01
	10^{-1}	Id	329.67	89.30	2.59	544.01	54.91	88.70	0.41	552.01
		Hess	/	90.13	3.62	651.01	/	92.26	0.54	627.01
	1	Id	1021.90	89.80	8.19	544.01	157.90	92.20	1.30	552.01
		Hess	/	87.00	12.05	651.01	/	87.12	1.69	627.01
HS42	10^{-4}	Id	5.71	99.50	0.12	235.20	0.79	99.83	0.02	240.00
		Hess	3.52	94.00	0.04	289.60	0.51	92.67	0.01	288.01
	10^{-2}	Id	53.13	100.00	1.17	235.20	8.64	99.83	0.17	240.00
		Hess	34.27	94.17	0.36	289.60	5.62	92.67	0.06	288.01
	10^{-1}	Id	181.17	99.67	3.69	235.20	27.12	99.67	0.55	240.00
		Hess	112.10	92.33	1.14	289.60	18.17	93.83	0.18	288.00
	1	Id	530.18	99.67	11.68	235.20	88.91	100.00	1.75	240.00
		Hess	349.85	90.67	3.57	289.60	53.69	96.00	0.56	288.00

C.2. Local normality and inference

We follow the discussion of Section 5 and show the local convergence behavior of DF-SSQP on more CUTEst problems. The results are summarized in Table 2. The findings and explanation from the table directly follow Section 5.

D. Preliminary Lemmas

LEMMA 8 (Ruszczynski (1980), Lemma 1). Let (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) be a probability space and let $\{\mathcal{F}_k\}$ be an increasing sequence of σ -algebras contained in \mathcal{F} . Let $\{\eta_k, z_k\}$ be sequences of \mathcal{F}_k -measurable \mathbb{R}^d -valued random variables satisfying the relations

$$\begin{aligned} z_{k+1} &= \Pi_Z((1 - \rho_k)z_k + \rho_k \xi_k), \quad z_0 \in Z, \\ \mathbb{E}[\xi_k | \mathcal{F}_k] &= \eta_k + b_k, \end{aligned}$$

where $\rho_k \geq 0$, the set $Z \subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ is convex and closed, and $\Pi_Z(\cdot)$ is the projection onto the set Z . Suppose the following conditions hold:

- (a) all accumulation points of the sequence η_k belong to Z almost surely;
- (b) there exists a constant C such that $E[\|\xi_k\|^2 | \mathcal{F}_k] \leq C$ for all $k \geq 0$;
- (c) $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{E}[\rho_k^2 + \rho_k \|b_k\|] < \infty$ and $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \rho_k = \infty$ almost surely;
- (d) $\|\eta_{k+1} - \eta_k\|/\rho_k \rightarrow 0$ almost surely.

Then, we have $z_k - \eta_k \rightarrow 0$ almost surely.

LEMMA 9 (Adapted from (Na and Mahoney 2025, Lemma B.3)). Let $\alpha_k = \iota_1(k+1)^{-p_1}$ and $\beta_k = \iota_2(k+1)^{-p_2}$ be two sequences with $\iota_1, \iota_2, p_1, p_2 > 0$. The following results hold.

- (a) Let $\chi = 0$ if $0 < p_2 < 1$ and $\chi = -p_1/\iota_2$ if $p_2 = 1$. Then, as long as $\sum_{t=1}^l a_t + \chi > 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\alpha_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k \prod_{t=1}^l (1 - a_t \beta_j) \beta_i \alpha_i &= \frac{1}{\sum_{t=1}^l a_t + \chi}, \\ \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\alpha_k} \left\{ \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k \prod_{t=1}^l (1 - a_t \beta_j) \beta_i \alpha_i e_i + b \prod_{j=0}^k \prod_{t=1}^l (1 - a_t \beta_j) \right\} &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

where the second result holds for any constant b and sequence $\{e_i\}$ such that $e_i \rightarrow 0$.

(b) If $0 < p_2 < p_1 \leq 1$, then

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\alpha_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \alpha_j) (1 - \beta_j) \alpha_i \beta_i = 1.$$

LEMMA 10. Let $B \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ and $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times d}$. Suppose $AA^T \succeq \gamma_A I$, $\|B\| \leq \Upsilon_B$ for some constants $\gamma_A, \Upsilon_B > 0$, and $Z \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times (d-m)}$ is a matrix whose columns are orthonormal and form the basis of $\text{Null}(A)$. Then,

$$Z^T B Z \succeq \gamma_{RH} I \implies \text{there exists } \delta = \delta(\gamma_{RH}, \gamma_A, \Upsilon_A) \text{ such that } B + \delta A^T A \succeq 0.5 \gamma_{RH} I.$$

Proof For any $z \in \mathbb{R}^d$, we decompose z as

$$z = \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y}, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{x} \in \text{Null}(A) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{y} \in \text{Range}(A^T). \quad (\text{D.1})$$

Then, we can see that

$$\begin{aligned} & z^T (B + \delta A^T A - 0.5 \gamma_{RH} I) z \\ & \stackrel{(\text{D.1})}{=} \mathbf{x}^T B \mathbf{x} + 2 \mathbf{x}^T B \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{y}^T B \mathbf{y} + \delta \|A(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{y})\|^2 - 0.5 \gamma_{RH} (\|\mathbf{x}\|^2 + \|\mathbf{y}\|^2) \\ & \geq 0.5 \gamma_{RH} \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 - 2 \Upsilon_B \|\mathbf{x}\| \cdot \|\mathbf{y}\| - \Upsilon_B \|\mathbf{y}\|^2 + \delta \gamma_A \|\mathbf{y}\|^2 - 0.5 \gamma_{RH} \|\mathbf{y}\|^2 \\ & = 0.5 \gamma_{RH} \left(\|\mathbf{x}\| - \frac{2 \Upsilon_B}{\gamma_{RH}} \|\mathbf{y}\| \right)^2 + \left(\delta \gamma_A - \Upsilon_B - 0.5 \gamma_{RH} - \frac{2 \Upsilon_B^2}{\gamma_{RH}} \right) \|\mathbf{y}\|^2, \end{aligned}$$

where the inequality follows from $Z^T B Z \succeq \gamma_{RH} I$, $\|B\| \leq \Upsilon_B$ and $AA^T \succeq \gamma_A I$. Therefore, $B + \delta A^T A \succeq 0.5 \gamma_{RH} I$ as long as $\delta \geq (\Upsilon_B + 0.5 \gamma_{RH} + 2 \Upsilon_B^2 / \gamma_{RH}) / \gamma_A$. ■

E. Supporting Lemmas

In this section, we present some supporting lemmas for proving the results in Sections 3 and 4. Let us first introduce some additional notation. We define $\mathcal{F}_{-1} \subseteq \mathcal{F}_0 \subseteq \mathcal{F}_1 \cdots$ as a filtration of σ -algebras, where $\mathcal{F}_k = \sigma(\{\xi_i, \Delta_i, \tilde{\Delta}_i\}_{i=0}^k)$, $\forall k \geq 0$ contains all the randomness before performing the $(k+1)$ -th iteration, and $\mathcal{F}_{-1} = \sigma(\{\mathbf{x}_0, \lambda_0\})$ is the trivial σ -algebra. For a random vector/matrix sequence $\{Y_k\}$ and a deterministic scalar sequence $\{y_k\}$, we write $Y_k = O(y_k)$ if $\|Y_k\|/y_k$ is uniformly bounded over sample paths. Additionally, $O_p(\cdot)$ and $o_p(\cdot)$ denote big- and little- O notation in probability sense, respectively.

Our first result characterizes the bias of the randomized gradient and Hessian approximations. We observe that the conditional bias converges to zero as k goes to infinity almost surely.

LEMMA 11. Under Assumptions 1, 2, 3, we have for $1 \leq j \leq m$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) - \nabla f_k \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] &= O(b_k^2), & \mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nabla} c_k - \nabla c_k \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] &= O(b_k^2), \\ \mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) - \nabla^2 f_k \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] &= O(b_k + \tilde{b}_k^2 / b_k), & \mathbb{E}[\tilde{\nabla}^2 c_k^j - \nabla^2 c_k^j \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] &= O(b_k + \tilde{b}_k^2 / b_k). \end{aligned}$$

Proof See Appendix F.1. ■

Let us decompose the direction step $\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k$ in (13) as a tangential step \mathbf{u}_k and a normal step \mathbf{v}_k as

$$\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k = \mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{v}_k, \quad \text{where } \mathbf{u}_k \in \text{Null}(\tilde{G}_k) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{v}_k \in \text{Range}(\tilde{G}_k^T). \quad (\text{E.1})$$

The next lemma establishes an upper bound for \mathbf{v}_k in terms of c_k in (i), a lower bound for the curvature of \tilde{B}_k along $\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k$ in terms of \mathbf{u}_k in (ii), and a lower bound on the reduction of the local model in (iii).

LEMMA 12. Under Assumption 1, there exist constants $\kappa_v, \kappa_u, \kappa_q > 0$ such that the following statements hold true for all $k \geq 0$.

- (a) \mathbf{v}_k satisfies $\max\{\|\mathbf{v}_k\|, \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2\} \leq \kappa_v \|c_k\|$.
- (b) If $\|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 \geq \kappa_u \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2$, then $\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k^T \tilde{B}_k \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k \geq 0.5 \kappa_{1, \tilde{B}} \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2$.
- (c) The reduction of the local model satisfies $\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) \geq \kappa_q \tau_k (\|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 + \|c_k\|)$.

Proof See Appendix F.4. ■

In local convergence analysis, the convergence rate of the iterate in Lemma 7 leads to the local convergence rate of the Hessian approximation.

LEMMA 13. *Under the setup of Lemma 7 and additionally supposing Assumptions 5, 6 hold and $p_4 > 0.5p_3$, we have*

$$\|\tilde{W}_k - W^*\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}(\epsilon) > k} = O_p\left(\beta_k + b_k^2 + \tilde{b}_k^4/b_k^2\right).$$

Proof See Appendix G.6. ■

F. Proofs of Section 3

F.1. Proof of Lemma 11

We use the objective gradient estimation as an example, while the same analysis applies to the constraint Jacobian. Our analysis is entrywise. Recall that for any vector v , v^i denotes the i -th entry of v . For any $1 \leq i \leq d$, we apply Taylor's expansion and have

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}F^i(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) - \nabla f_k^i \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \\ & \stackrel{(2)}{=} \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{F(\mathbf{x}_k + b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k) - F(\mathbf{x}_k - b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k)}{2b_k \Delta_k^i} - \nabla f_k^i \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}\right] \\ & = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{f(\mathbf{x}_k + b_k \Delta_k) - f(\mathbf{x}_k - b_k \Delta_k)}{2b_k \Delta_k^i} - \nabla f_k^i \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}\right] \quad (\text{by Assumption 2}) \\ & = \frac{1}{12} \mathbb{E}\left[(b_k \Delta_k^i)^{-1} \sum_{i_1} \sum_{i_2} \sum_{i_3} b_k^3 [\nabla^3 f(\mathbf{x}_k^+) + \nabla^3 f(\mathbf{x}_k^-)]^{i_1 i_2 i_3} \Delta_k^{i_1} \Delta_k^{i_2} \Delta_k^{i_3} \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}\right], \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.1})$$

where \mathbf{x}_k^\pm are some points lying on the line segments between \mathbf{x}_k and $\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k$, respectively, and the last equality also applies the symmetry condition on Δ_k in Assumption 3. By the boundedness of Δ_k in Assumption 3 and boundedness of $\nabla^3 f$ in Assumption 1, we further have

$$\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}F^i(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) - \nabla f_k^i \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \stackrel{(\text{F.1})}{=} O\left(\frac{b_k^2}{6} \sum_{i_1} \sum_{i_2} \sum_{i_3} \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{\Delta_k^{i_1} \Delta_k^{i_2} \Delta_k^{i_3}}{\Delta_k^i}\right]\right) = O(b_k^2). \quad (\text{F.2})$$

This completes the proof of the first part of the lemma. Now, we consider objective Hessian estimation, while noting that the same analysis applies directly to the constraint Hessian. For any $1 \leq \ell_1, \ell_2 \leq d$, we know

$$\mathbb{E}\left[\frac{\delta \widehat{\nabla}F^{\ell_1}(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k)}{2b_k \Delta_k^{\ell_2}} \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}\right] \stackrel{(8)}{=} \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{\widehat{\nabla}F^{\ell_1}(\mathbf{x}_k + b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k) - \widehat{\nabla}F^{\ell_1}(\mathbf{x}_k - b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k)}{2b_k \Delta_k^{\ell_2}} \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}\right].$$

Applying the definition (6) and following the same analysis as in (F.1) and (F.2), we can have

$$\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}F^{\ell_1}(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k) \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}, \Delta_k] = \nabla f^{\ell_1}(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k) + O(\tilde{b}_k^2).$$

Combining the above two displays and applying the Taylor's expansion, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{\delta \widehat{\nabla}F^{\ell_1}(\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k; \xi_k)}{2b_k \Delta_k^{\ell_2}} - \nabla^2 f_k^{\ell_1 \ell_2} \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}\right] \\ & = \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{\nabla f^{\ell_1}(\mathbf{x}_k + b_k \Delta_k) - \nabla f^{\ell_1}(\mathbf{x}_k - b_k \Delta_k)}{2b_k \Delta_k^{\ell_2}} - \nabla^2 f_k^{\ell_1 \ell_2} \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}\right] + O(\tilde{b}_k^2/b_k) \\ & = \frac{1}{4} \mathbb{E}\left[(b_k \Delta_k^{\ell_2})^{-1} \sum_{i_1} \sum_{i_2} b_k^2 [\nabla^2(\nabla f^{\ell_1})(\mathbf{x}_k^+) + \nabla^2(\nabla f^{\ell_1})(\mathbf{x}_k^-)]^{i_1 i_2} \Delta_k^{i_1} \Delta_k^{i_2} \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}\right] + O(\tilde{b}_k^2/b_k) \\ & = O(b_k + \tilde{b}_k^2/b_k), \end{aligned}$$

where we abuse the notation \mathbf{x}_k^\pm in the second equality from (F.1) to let it denote some points lying on the line segments between \mathbf{x}_k and $\mathbf{x}_k \pm b_k \Delta_k$, and the second equality also applies Assumption 3. The last equality is due to Assumptions 1 and 3. This completes the proof.

F.2. Proof of Lemma 1

By Assumption 1, let us denote $\Upsilon_{\nabla f} > 0$ such that $\|\nabla f(\mathbf{x})\| \leq \Upsilon_{\nabla f}$, $\forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}$. We use $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k$ as an example, while the same analysis applies to \bar{G}_k . We note that $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k$ satisfies the following relations:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k &\stackrel{(5)}{=} (1 - \beta_k)\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{k-1} + \beta_k \widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k), \\ \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] &= \nabla f_k + O(b_k^2) \quad (\text{by Lemma 11}). \end{aligned}$$

We establish the almost sure convergence of $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k$ by applying Lemma 8. We check the conditions in Lemma 8. Note that condition (a) in Lemma 8 is trivially satisfied. For condition (b), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k)\|^2 &\stackrel{(2)}{=} \left\| \frac{1}{2b_k} \int_{-b_k}^{b_k} \langle \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k; \xi_k), \Delta_k \rangle \Delta_k^{-1} ds \right\|^2 \\ &\leq \|\Delta_k^{-1}\|^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2b_k} \int_{-b_k}^{b_k} \|\langle \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k; \xi_k), \Delta_k \rangle\|^2 ds \\ &\leq \|\Delta_k^{-1}\|^2 \|\Delta_k\|^2 \frac{1}{2b_k} \int_{-b_k}^{b_k} \|\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k; \xi_k)\|^2 ds, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.3})$$

where the first inequality is due to the Jensen's inequality. For any $s \in [-b_k, b_k]$, we know from Assumption 2(19a) with $r \geq 2$ in (20) that

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathbb{E}[\|\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k; \xi_k)\|^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}, \Delta_k] \\ &\leq 2\mathbb{E}[\|\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k; \xi_k) - \nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k)\|^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}, \Delta_k] + 2\|\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k)\|^2 \\ &\leq 2\{\mathbb{E}[\|\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k; \xi_k) - \nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k)\|^r \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}, \Delta_k]\}^{2/r} + 2\Upsilon_{\nabla f}^2 \\ &\leq 2(\Upsilon_m^{2/r} + \Upsilon_{\nabla f}^2). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.4})$$

Combining (F.3) and (F.4), and applying Assumption 3, we obtain

$$\mathbb{E}[\|\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k)\|^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \leq 2d^2 \kappa_{\Delta_2}^2 \kappa_{\Delta_1}^{-2} (\Upsilon_m^{2/r} + \Upsilon_{\nabla f}^2), \quad (\text{F.5})$$

which verifies condition (b). Condition (c) is immediately satisfied under the conditions $p_2 \in (0.5, 1]$ and $p_2 + 2p_3 > 1$ in (20) of the lemma. For condition (d), we note for the Lipschitz constant $\kappa_{\nabla f} > 0$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \|\nabla f_{k+1} - \nabla f_k\| &\leq \kappa_{\nabla f} \|\mathbf{x}_{k+1} - \mathbf{x}_k\| \quad (\text{Lipschitz property}) \\ &= \kappa_{\nabla f} \bar{\alpha}_k \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| \stackrel{(13),(18)}{\leq} \kappa_{\nabla f} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1} \alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \|\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\| (\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\| + \|c_k\|). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.6})$$

By Assumption 1 and (Na et al. 2022, Lemma 1), there exists a constant $\Upsilon_K > 0$ such that $\|\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\| \leq \Upsilon_K$, $\forall k \geq 0$, and also $\|c_k\| \leq \kappa_c$. Furthermore, we follow the same analysis as in (F.3), (F.4), (F.5), and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\|\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k)\|^r \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\|\Delta_k^{-1}\|^r \|\Delta_k\|^r \frac{1}{2b_k} \int_{-b_k}^{b_k} \|\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k; \xi_k)\|^r ds \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1} \right] \\ &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\|\Delta_k^{-1}\|^r \|\Delta_k\|^r \frac{2^{r-1}}{2b_k} \int_{-b_k}^{b_k} (\|\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k; \xi_k) - \nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k)\|^r + \|\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_k + s\Delta_k)\|^r) ds \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1} \right] \\ &\leq 2^{r-1} d^r \kappa_{\Delta_2}^r \kappa_{\Delta_1}^{-r} (\Upsilon_m + \Upsilon_{\nabla f}^r). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.7})$$

Thus, let us define

$$\Upsilon_{\bar{\mathbf{g}}} := \max\{\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{-1}\|^r, 2^{r-1} d^r \kappa_{\Delta_2}^r \kappa_{\Delta_1}^{-r} (\Upsilon_m + \Upsilon_{\nabla f}^r)\}. \quad (\text{F.8})$$

Then, we know $\mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{-1}\|^r] = \|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{-1}\|^r \leq \Upsilon_{\bar{\mathbf{g}}}$. For any $k \geq 0$, suppose $\mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{k-1}\|^r] \leq \Upsilon_{\bar{\mathbf{g}}}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\|^r] &\leq \mathbb{E}[\|(1 - \beta_k)\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{k-1} + \beta_k \widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k)\|^r] \\ &\leq (1 - \beta_k) \mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{k-1}\|^r] + \beta_k \mathbb{E}[\|\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k)\|^r] \stackrel{(F.7)}{\leq} \Upsilon_{\bar{\mathbf{g}}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.9})$$

This shows $\mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\|^r] \leq \Upsilon_{\bar{\mathbf{g}}}$ for any $k \geq 0$. Combining the above display with (F.6), and noting that $p \geq 1$, we obtain

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\|\nabla f_{k+1} - \nabla f_k\|^r}{\beta_k^r} \right] = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_{k+1} - \nabla f_k\|^r]}{\beta_k^r}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\kappa_{\nabla f}^r \left(\frac{\gamma_{-1} \alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right)^r \Upsilon_K^r 2^{r-1} (\mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\|^r] + \mathbb{E}[\|c_k\|^r])}{\beta_k^r} \\
&\leq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\kappa_{\nabla f}^r \left(\frac{\gamma_{-1}}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^{p-1} \right)^r \Upsilon_K^r 2^{r-1} (\Upsilon_{\bar{\mathbf{g}}} + \kappa_c^r) \alpha_k^r}{\beta_k^r} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} O\left(\frac{\alpha_k^r}{\beta_k^r}\right) < \infty, \tag{F.10}
\end{aligned}$$

where the first equality is due to Tonelli's theorem and the last inequality is due to $r(p_1 - p_2) > 1$ in (20). The above result immediately implies $\|\nabla f_{k+1} - \nabla f_k\|/\beta_k \rightarrow 0$ almost surely, which verifies condition (d). By Lemma 8, we have $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$ almost surely. The same analysis applies to \bar{G}_k , and we complete the proof for the first part of the lemma. For the second part, we know for each sample path, there exists $K_G^* > 0$ such that for any $k \geq K_G^*$,

$$\|\bar{G}_k \bar{G}_k^T - G_k G_k^T\| \leq \min\{\kappa_{2,\bar{G}} - \kappa_{2,G}, \kappa_{1,G} - \kappa_{1,\bar{G}}\}.$$

By Weyl's inequality (Horn and Johnson 1985, Theorem 4.3.1), we know $\kappa_{1,\bar{G}} \cdot I \preceq \bar{G}_k \bar{G}_k^T \preceq \kappa_{2,\bar{G}} \cdot I$. Since the modification δ_k^G is introduced to modify \bar{G}_k to satisfy this condition, we know there is no need to apply δ_k^G for all $k \geq K_G^*$. This completes the proof.

F.3. Proof of Lemma 2

We use $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k$ as an example, while the same analysis applies to \bar{G}_k . We decompose $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k &\stackrel{(5)}{=} \beta_k (\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) - \nabla f_k) + (1 - \beta_k) (\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{k-1} - \nabla f_{k-1}) + (1 - \beta_k) (\nabla f_{k-1} - \nabla f_k) \\
&\stackrel{(5)}{=} \beta_k (\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) - \nabla f_k) + (1 - \beta_k) \{ \beta_{k-1} (\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}; \xi_{k-1}) - \nabla f_{k-1}) \\
&\quad + (1 - \beta_{k-1}) (\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{k-2} - \nabla f_{k-2}) + (1 - \beta_{k-1}) (\nabla f_{k-2} - \nabla f_{k-1}) \} + (1 - \beta_k) (\nabla f_{k-1} - \nabla f_k) \\
&= \dots \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \nabla f_i) + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i}^k (1 - \beta_j) (\nabla f_{i-1} - \nabla f_i) \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]) \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] - \nabla f_i) + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i}^k (1 - \beta_j) (\nabla f_{i-1} - \nabla f_i), \tag{F.11}
\end{aligned}$$

where we denote $\nabla f_{-1} = \bar{\mathbf{g}}_{-1}$ in the last two equalities for clarity. We now proceed to derive bounds for each term in (F.11). In particular, using the martingale difference property, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]) \right\|^2 \right] \\
&= \sum_{i=0}^k \left(\prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \right)^2 \beta_i^2 \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] \right\|^2 \right] \\
&\stackrel{(F.5)}{=} O \left(\sum_{i=0}^k \left(\prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \right)^2 \beta_i^2 \right) = O(\beta_k) \quad (\text{by Lemma 9}),
\end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality holds since if $p_2 = 1$, we have $2 - 1/\iota_2 > 0 \Leftrightarrow \iota_2 > 0.5$ as in (21). For the second term in (F.11), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left\| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] - \nabla f_i) \right\| \\
&\leq \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i \left\| \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] - \nabla f_i \right\| = O \left(\sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i b_i^2 \right) \quad (\text{by Lemma 11})
\end{aligned}$$

$$= O(b_k^2) \quad (\text{by Lemma 9}),$$

where the last inequality holds since if $p_2 = 1$, we have $1 - 2p_3/\iota_2 > 0 \Leftrightarrow p_3 < 0.5\iota_2$ as in (21). For the third term in (F.11), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i}^k (1 - \beta_j) (\nabla f_{i-1} - \nabla f_i) \right\|^2 \right] \leq \left(\sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i}^k (1 - \beta_j) \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_{i-1} - \nabla f_i\|^2]} \right)^2 \\ & \leq O \left(\left\{ \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i}^k (1 - \beta_j) \alpha_{i-1} \right\}^2 \right) \quad (\text{by the same analysis of (F.6), (F.7), (F.9), (F.10)}) \\ & = O \left(\frac{\alpha_k^2}{\beta_k^2} \right) \quad (\text{by Lemma 9}), \end{aligned}$$

where we set $\alpha_{-1} = \|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_{-1} - \nabla f_0\|$ in the last inequality and the last equality holds since $p_1 > p_2$, and if $p_2 = 1$, $1 - (p_1 - p_2)/\iota_2 > 0 \Leftrightarrow p_1 < p_2 + \iota_2$ as in (21). Combining the above three displays with (F.11), we know $\mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k\|^2] = O(\beta_k + b_k^4 + \alpha_k^2/\beta_k^2)$. The same analysis applies to \tilde{G}_k , thereby completing the proof.

F.4. Proof of Lemma 12

Let $k \geq 0$. For the result (a), we note that

$$\tilde{G}_k \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k \stackrel{(E.1)}{=} \tilde{G}_k (\mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{v}_k) \stackrel{(E.1)}{=} \tilde{G}_k \mathbf{v}_k \stackrel{(13)}{=} -c_k.$$

We apply Assumption 1 and have $\mathbf{v}_k = -\tilde{G}_k^T (\tilde{G}_k \tilde{G}_k^T)^{-1} c_k$. Thus, we obtain

$$\|\mathbf{v}_k\| \leq \|\tilde{G}_k^T (\tilde{G}_k \tilde{G}_k^T)^{-1}\| \|c_k\| \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{\kappa_{1,\tilde{G}}}} \|c_k\| \quad \text{and} \quad \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2 \leq \frac{1}{\kappa_{1,\tilde{G}}} \|c_k\|^2 \leq \frac{\kappa_c}{\kappa_{1,\tilde{G}}} \|c_k\|. \quad (\text{F.12})$$

Thus, (a) holds with $\kappa_v = \max\{1/\sqrt{\kappa_{1,\tilde{G}}}, \kappa_c/\kappa_{1,\tilde{G}}\}$. For the result (b), we note that

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k^T \tilde{B}_k \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k & \stackrel{(E.1)}{=} \mathbf{u}_k^T \tilde{B}_k \mathbf{u}_k + 2\mathbf{u}_k^T \tilde{B}_k \mathbf{v}_k + \mathbf{v}_k^T \tilde{B}_k \mathbf{v}_k \\ & \geq \kappa_{1,\tilde{B}} \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 - 2\kappa_{2,\tilde{B}} \|\mathbf{u}_k\| \|\mathbf{v}_k\| - \kappa_{2,\tilde{B}} \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2 \quad (\text{by Assumption 1}) \\ & \geq \left(\kappa_{1,\tilde{B}} - \frac{2\kappa_{2,\tilde{B}}}{\sqrt{\kappa_u}} - \frac{\kappa_{2,\tilde{B}}}{\kappa_u} \right) \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 \quad (\text{by } \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 \geq \kappa_u \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.13})$$

Thus, as long as κ_u is large enough such that $2\kappa_{2,\tilde{B}}/\sqrt{\kappa_u} + \kappa_{2,\tilde{B}}/\kappa_u \leq \kappa_{1,\tilde{B}}/2$, the result (b) holds. For the result (c), we note that

$$\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) \stackrel{(16)}{\geq} \frac{1}{2} \tau_k \max\{\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k^T \tilde{B}_k \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k, 0\} + \sigma \|c_k\|.$$

If $\|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 \geq \kappa_u \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) & \stackrel{(F.13)}{\geq} \frac{1}{4} \tau_k \kappa_{1,\tilde{B}} \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 + \sigma \|c_k\| \\ & \geq \frac{\tau_k \kappa_u \kappa_{1,\tilde{B}}}{4(1 + \kappa_u)} (\|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 + \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2) + \sigma \|c_k\| \quad (\text{by } \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 \geq \kappa_u \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2) \\ & \stackrel{(E.1)}{=} \frac{\tau_k \kappa_u \kappa_{1,\tilde{B}}}{4(1 + \kappa_u)} \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 + \sigma \|c_k\|. \end{aligned}$$

Otherwise, we have

$$\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) \geq \sigma \|c_k\| \stackrel{(F.12)}{\geq} \frac{\sigma}{2\kappa_v(1 + \kappa_u)} \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 + \frac{\sigma}{2} \|c_k\| \quad (\text{by } \|\mathbf{u}_k\|^2 \leq \kappa_u \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2).$$

Combining the above two displays, we know (c) holds for $\kappa_q = \min\{\kappa_u \kappa_{1,\tilde{B}}/4(1 + \kappa_u), \sigma/2\tau_{-1}, \sigma/\{2\kappa_v\tau_{-1}(1 + \kappa_u)\}\}$. This completes the proof.

F.5. Proof of Lemma 3

From the update of (15), we know $\tau_k < \tau_{k-1}$ if and only if both $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k + \max\{\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k^T \bar{B}_k \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k, 0\} > 0$ and $\tau_{k-1}(\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k + \max\{\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k^T \bar{B}_k \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k, 0\}) > (1 - \sigma)\|c_k\|$. From (13), we know

$$\bar{B}_k \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k + \bar{G}_k^T \bar{\Delta \lambda}_k = -\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \bar{G}_k^T \lambda_k.$$

Multiplying both sides by \mathbf{u}_k^T , we obtain

$$\mathbf{u}_k^T \bar{B}_k (\mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{v}_k) \stackrel{(E.1)}{=} -\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \mathbf{u}_k. \quad (F.14)$$

If $\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k^T \bar{B}_k \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k \geq 0$, we have for some $\kappa_{\tau,1} > 0$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k + \max\{\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k^T \bar{B}_k \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k, 0\} &\stackrel{(E.1)}{=} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T (\mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{v}_k) + (\mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{v}_k)^T \bar{B}_k (\mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{v}_k) \\ &\stackrel{(F.14)}{=} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \mathbf{v}_k + \mathbf{v}_k^T \bar{B}_k \mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{v}_k^T \bar{B}_k \mathbf{v}_k \\ &\leq (\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\| + \kappa_{2,\bar{B}} \|\mathbf{u}_k\|) \|\mathbf{v}_k\| + \kappa_{2,\bar{B}} \|\mathbf{v}_k\|^2 \quad (\text{by Assumption 1}) \\ &\leq \kappa_{\tau,1} \|c_k\|, \end{aligned}$$

where the existence of $\kappa_{\tau,1}$ in the last inequality is due to the boundedness of $\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k$ (similar to (F.9)), the boundedness of $\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k$ (hence \mathbf{u}_k) in (F.6), and Lemma 12(a). Otherwise $\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k^T \bar{B}_k \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k < 0$, we have for some $\kappa_{\tau,2} > 0$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k + \max\{\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k^T \bar{B}_k \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k, 0\} &\stackrel{(E.1)}{=} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T (\mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{v}_k) \\ &\stackrel{(F.14)}{=} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \mathbf{v}_k - \mathbf{u}_k^T \bar{B}_k \mathbf{u}_k - \mathbf{u}_k^T \bar{B}_k \mathbf{v}_k \\ &\leq (\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\| + \kappa_{2,\bar{B}} \|\mathbf{u}_k\|) \|\mathbf{v}_k\| \quad (\text{by Assumption 1}) \\ &\leq \kappa_{\tau,2} \|c_k\|, \end{aligned}$$

where the existence of $\kappa_{\tau,2}$ in the last inequality follows from the same reasoning as $\kappa_{\tau,1}$. Combining the above two displays, we know that, to have $\tau_k < \tau_{k-1}$, we must have $\tau_{k-1} > (1 - \sigma) / \max\{\kappa_{\tau,1}, \kappa_{\tau,2}\}$. This, combined with the fact that Algorithm 1 decreases τ_k by at least a constant factor whenever it is reduced, implies the existence of a (potentially random) $K_\tau^* > 0$ such that $\tau_k = \tau_{K_\tau^*} \geq \tilde{\tau} = (1 - \sigma) / \max\{\kappa_{\tau,1}, \kappa_{\tau,2}\}$ for all $k \geq K_\tau^*$. We now proceed to prove the stabilization of \mathbf{v}_k . By Lemma 12(c) and the lower bound of τ_k demonstrated above, we have

$$\nu_k^{\text{trial}} \stackrel{(17)}{=} \frac{\Delta q(\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \bar{B}_k)}{\|\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\|^2} \geq \frac{\kappa_q \tau_k (\|\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\|^2 + \|c_k\|)}{\|\bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\|^2} \geq \kappa_q \tau_k \geq \kappa_q \tilde{\tau}.$$

This, combined with the fact that Algorithm 1 decreases ν_k by at least a constant factor whenever it is reduced, implies the existence of a (potentially random) $K_\nu^* > 0$ such that ν_k stabilizes as $\nu_k = \nu_{K_\nu^*} \geq \tilde{\nu} = (1 - \varepsilon) \kappa_q \tilde{\tau}$ for all $k \geq K_\nu^*$. Letting $K_{\tau\nu}^* = \max\{K_\tau^*, K_\nu^*\}$ completes the proof.

F.6. Proof of Lemma 4

By Assumption 4 and noting that $p \geq 1$ in (18), we know there exists a (deterministic) $K_1^* > 0$ such that $\nu_{-1} \alpha_k / \kappa_{\nabla c} + \psi \alpha_k^p \leq 1$ for all $k \geq K_1^*$. We further apply Lemmas 1 and 3, and know that there exist (potentially random) $K_G^*, K_{\tau\nu}^* < \infty$ such that $\bar{G}_k = \bar{G}_k$, $\tau_k = \tau_{K_{\tau\nu}^*}$, and $\nu_k = \nu_{K_{\tau\nu}^*}$ for all $k \geq \max\{K_G^*, K_{\tau\nu}^*\}$. To proceed, we first validate the well-definedness of $(\Delta \mathbf{x}_k, \Delta \lambda_k)$. By Lemma 10 and Assumption 1, we know there exists $\delta = \delta(\kappa_{1,\bar{G}}, \kappa_{1,\bar{B}}, \kappa_{2,\bar{B}})$ such that $\bar{B}_k + \delta \bar{G}_k^T \bar{G}_k \geq 0.5 \kappa_{1,\bar{B}} I$. Since we have from Lemma 1 that $\bar{G}_k - G_k \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely, there exists (potentially random) $K_2^* < \infty$ such that $\bar{B}_k + \delta G_k^T G_k \geq 0.25 \kappa_{1,\bar{B}} I$ for all $k \geq K_2^*$, which implies $\bar{B}_k \geq 0.25 \kappa_{1,\bar{B}} I$ in $\text{Null}(G_k)$. This result, combined with $\kappa_{1,G} I \preceq G_k G_k^T \preceq \kappa_{2,G} I$ in Assumption 1, implies that $(\Delta \mathbf{x}_k, \Delta \lambda_k)$ is well-defined. Furthermore, following the same analysis as in (F.6), we have

$$\|W_k^{-1}\| := \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \bar{B}_k & G_k^T \\ G_k & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \right\| \leq \Upsilon_K \quad \text{and} \quad \|\Delta \mathbf{x}_k\| \leq \Upsilon_K (\Upsilon_{\nabla f} + \kappa_c), \quad (F.15)$$

where we abuse the notation Υ_K in the analysis (F.6) to denote a common upper bound for \bar{W}_k^{-1} and W_k^{-1} , and $\Upsilon_{\nabla f}$ denotes the upper bound of ∇f in the analysis of (F.4). We now proceed to establish the convergence guarantee for $k \geq K^* := \max\{K_1^*, K_2^*, K_G^*, K_{\tau\nu}^*\}$. We have

$$\phi_{\tau_{K_{\tau\nu}^*}}(\mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \bar{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k) - \phi_{\tau_{K_{\tau\nu}^*}}(\mathbf{x}_k)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} f(\mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k) + \|c(\mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k)\| - \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} f(\mathbf{x}_k) - \|c(\mathbf{x}_k)\| \\
 &\leq \bar{\alpha}_k \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \nabla f_k^T \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k + \|c_k + \bar{\alpha}_k G_k \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| - \|c_k\| + \frac{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}}{2} \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \quad (\text{Lipschitz property}) \\
 &\leq \bar{\alpha}_k \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \nabla f_k^T \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k + \|c_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \bar{G}_k \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| + \bar{\alpha}_k \|G_k - \bar{G}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| - \|c_k\| + \frac{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}}{2} \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \\
 &\stackrel{(13)}{=} \bar{\alpha}_k \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \nabla f_k^T \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k + |1 - \bar{\alpha}_k| \|c_k\| - \|c_k\| + \bar{\alpha}_k \|G_k - \bar{G}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| + \frac{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}}{2} \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \\
 &= \bar{\alpha}_k \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \nabla f_k^T \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k \|c_k\| + \bar{\alpha}_k \|G_k - \bar{G}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| + \frac{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}}{2} \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \quad (\text{by } \bar{\alpha}_k \leq 1) \\
 &= \bar{\alpha}_k \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k^T \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} (\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k)^T \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k \|c_k\| + \bar{\alpha}_k \|G_k - \bar{G}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| + \frac{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}}{2} \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \\
 &\stackrel{(14)}{\leq} -\bar{\alpha}_k \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k; \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*}, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \bar{B}_k) + \bar{\alpha}_k \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} (\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k)^T \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \|G_k - \bar{G}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| \\
 &\quad + \frac{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}}{2} \bar{\alpha}_k^2 \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \\
 &\stackrel{(18)}{\leq} -\frac{\nu_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \alpha_k}{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k; \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*}, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \bar{B}_k) + \left(\frac{\nu_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \alpha_k}{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \|(\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k)\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| \\
 &\quad + \left(\frac{\nu_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \alpha_k}{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \|G_k - \bar{G}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| + \frac{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}}{2} \left(\frac{\nu_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \alpha_k}{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right)^2 \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Taking conditional expectation $\mathbb{E}[\cdot | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}]$ and subtracting f_{inf} in Assumption 1 on both sides, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathbb{E}[\phi_{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*}}(\mathbf{x}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k) - f_{\text{inf}} | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \leq \phi_{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*}}(\mathbf{x}_k) - f_{\text{inf}} - \frac{\nu_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \alpha_k}{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} \mathbb{E}[\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k; \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*}, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \bar{B}_k) | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \\
 &\quad + \left(\frac{\nu_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \alpha_k}{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \left\{ \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] + \mathbb{E}[\|G_k - \bar{G}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \right\} \\
 &\quad + \frac{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}}{2} \left(\frac{\nu_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \alpha_k}{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right)^2 \mathbb{E}[\|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \\
 &\leq \phi_{\tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*}}(\mathbf{x}_k) - f_{\text{inf}} - \frac{\bar{\nu} \alpha_k}{\tau_{-1} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} \mathbb{E}[\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k; \tau_{K_{\tau_v}^*}, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \bar{B}_k) | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \\
 &\quad + \left(\frac{\nu_{-1} \alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \left\{ \tau_{-1} \mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] + \mathbb{E}[\|G_k - \bar{G}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \right\} \\
 &\quad + \frac{\tau_{-1} \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}}{2} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1} \alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right)^2 \mathbb{E}[\|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}], \tag{F.16}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality utilizes Lemma 3. We now derive bounds for each positive conditional expectation term in (F.16) so that we can apply Robbins-Siegmund theorem (Robbins and Siegmund 1985). In particular, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1} \alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \tau_{-1} \mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\| | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \right] \\
 &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1} \alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \tau_{-1} \mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|] \quad (\text{by Tonelli's theorem}) \\
 &\leq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1} \alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \tau_{-1} \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\|^2]} \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_k\|^2]} \quad (\text{by Cauchy-Schwarz inequality}) \\
 &\stackrel{(F.8)}{\leq} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1} \alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \tau_{-1} \Upsilon_K \sqrt{2} (\Upsilon_{\bar{\mathbf{g}}}^{1/r} + \kappa_c) \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\|^2]} \quad (\text{by the same analysis of (F.10)}) \\
 &\leq \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1} \alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \tau_{-1} \Upsilon_K (\Upsilon_{\bar{\mathbf{g}}} + \kappa_c) \left(\sqrt{\beta_k} + b_k^2 + \frac{\alpha_k}{\beta_k} \right) \quad (\text{by Lemma 2}) \\
 &< \infty, \tag{F.17}
 \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality is ensured by $p \geq 1$, and $p_1 + 0.5p_2 > 1$, $p_1 + 2p_3 > 1$, $2p_1 - p_2 > 1$, as assumed in (22) in the statement of the lemma. Therefore, we immediately have

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1}\alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi\alpha_k^p \right) \tau_{-1} \mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\| \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \right] < \infty \quad (\text{F.18})$$

and hence

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1}\alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi\alpha_k^p \right) \tau_{-1} \mathbb{E}[\|\nabla f_k - \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\| \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \mid \mathcal{F}_{K^*-1} \right] < \infty \quad \text{almost surely.}$$

Following the same analysis as in (F.17) and (F.18), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1}\alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi\alpha_k^p \right) \mathbb{E}[\|G_k - \bar{G}_k\| \|\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\| \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \mid \mathcal{F}_{K^*-1} \right] &< \infty \quad \text{almost surely,} \\ \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu_{-1}\alpha_k}{\kappa_{\nabla c}} + \psi\alpha_k^p \right)^2 \mathbb{E}[\|\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\|^2 \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \mid \mathcal{F}_{K^*-1} \right] &< \infty \quad \text{almost surely.} \end{aligned}$$

Combining the above two displays with (F.16), we have from Robbins-Siegmund theorem (Robbins and Siegmund 1985) that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k \mathbb{E} \left[\mathbb{E}[\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k; \tau_{K^*_{\tau\nu}}, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) \mid \mathcal{F}_{k-1}] \mid \mathcal{F}_{K^*-1} \right] \\ = \sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k \mathbb{E}[\Delta q(\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k; \tau_{K^*_{\tau\nu}}, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) \mid \mathcal{F}_{K^*-1}] < \infty, \end{aligned}$$

which implies $P(\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k; \tau_{K^*_{\tau\nu}}, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) < \infty \mid \mathcal{F}_{K^*-1}) = 1$. Since the result holds for any \mathcal{F}_{K^*-1} , we integrate out the randomness of \mathcal{F}_{K^*-1} and obtain

$$\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k; \tau_{K^*_{\tau\nu}}, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) < \infty \quad \text{almost surely.}$$

Utilizing $\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k = \infty$ for any run of the algorithm, we know $\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} \Delta q(\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k; \tau_k, \mathbf{x}_k, \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k, \tilde{B}_k) = 0$ almost surely. Furthermore, by Lemma 12(c) and Lemma 3, we know that $\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k (\|\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\|^2 + \|c_k\|) < \infty$ almost surely. On the other hand, we note for $k \geq K^*$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k - \Delta \mathbf{x}_k\| &\stackrel{(13)}{\leq} \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{B}_k & \tilde{G}_k^T \\ \tilde{G}_k & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k \\ c_k \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{B}_k & G_k^T \\ G_k & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f_k \\ c_k \end{pmatrix} \right\| \\ &\leq \Upsilon_K^2 \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \tilde{G}_k^T - G_k^T \\ \tilde{G}_k - G_k & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\| \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f_k \\ c_k \end{pmatrix} \right\| + \Upsilon_K \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\| \\ &\leq 2\Upsilon_K^2 (\Upsilon_{\nabla f} + \kappa_c) \|\tilde{G}_k - G_k\| + \Upsilon_K \|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k\|, \end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality is due to the boundedness of ∇f_k (cf. (F.4)) and the boundedness of c_k in Assumption 1. Following the same analysis as in (F.17) and applying Lemma 2, we have

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \alpha_k (\|\tilde{G}_k - G_k\|^2 + \|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k\|^2) \right] < \infty.$$

The above two displays imply $\mathbb{E}[\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k \|\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k - \Delta \mathbf{x}_k\|^2] < \infty$ and thus, $\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k \|\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k - \Delta \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 < \infty$ almost surely. With this result and $\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k (\|\Delta \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 + \|c_k\|) < \infty$, we have almost surely

$$\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k (\|\Delta \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 + \|c_k\|) \leq \sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k (2\|\tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\|^2 + \|c_k\|) + 2 \sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k \|\Delta \mathbf{x}_k - \tilde{\Delta \mathbf{x}}_k\|^2 < \infty.$$

Utilizing $\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k = \infty$ for any run of the algorithm, we obtain $\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\|\Delta \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 + \|c_k\|) = 0$ almost surely. This completes the proof.

F.7. Proof of Theorem 1

Let us consider $k \geq K^* := \max\{K_1^*, K_2^*, K_G^*, K_{\tau\nu}^*\}$ and define $\lambda_k^{\text{sub}} = \lambda_k + \Delta\lambda_k$. By (13), replacing \bar{g}_k with ∇f_k and \tilde{G}_k with G_k , we have $\tilde{B}_k \Delta \mathbf{x}_k + G_k^T \Delta \lambda_k = -\nabla f_k - G_k^T \lambda_k$. By Assumption 1, we have

$$\|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\text{sub}}\| = \|\tilde{B}_k \Delta \mathbf{x}_k\| \leq \kappa_{2, \tilde{B}} \|\Delta \mathbf{x}_k\|.$$

By Lemma 4, we know $\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k (\|\Delta \mathbf{x}_k\|^2 + \|c_k\|) < \infty$; thus, $\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k (\|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\text{sub}}\|^2 + \|c_k\|) < \infty$ almost surely. Furthermore, if we define $\lambda_k^{\star \text{true}} = -[G_k G_k^T]^{-1} G_k \nabla f_k$, which is indeed well-defined based on Assumption 1, then

$$\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k (\|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\|^2 + \|c_k\|) \leq \sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k (\|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\text{sub}}\|^2 + \|c_k\|) < \infty. \quad (\text{F.19})$$

Together with $\sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \alpha_k = \infty$, we know almost surely

$$\liminf_{k \rightarrow \infty} (\|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\|^2 + \|c_k\|) = 0.$$

We claim $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\| + \|c_k\| = 0$, and use $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\| = 0$ as an example; the same analysis applies to $\|c_k\|$. Suppose $\limsup_{k \rightarrow \infty} [\|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\|] > 0$. For such a run, we can find a sufficiently small number $\epsilon^* > 0$ and two infinite sequences $\{m_i\}$ and $\{n_i\}$ with $K^* < m_i < n_i, \forall i \geq 0$, such that

$$\|\nabla f_{m_i} + G_{m_i}^T \lambda_{m_i}^{\star \text{true}}\| \geq 2\epsilon^*, \quad \|\nabla f_{n_i} + G_{n_i}^T \lambda_{n_i}^{\star \text{true}}\| < \epsilon^*, \quad \|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\| \geq \epsilon^* \quad \text{for } k \in [m_i, n_i). \quad (\text{F.20})$$

Then, we have for some (potentially random) constant $\Upsilon > 0$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon^* &\stackrel{(\text{F.20})}{\leq} \|(\nabla f_{m_i} + G_{m_i}^T \lambda_{m_i}^{\star \text{true}})\| - \|\nabla f_{n_i} + G_{n_i}^T \lambda_{n_i}^{\star \text{true}}\| \\ &= \sum_{k=m_i}^{n_i-1} \left(\|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\| - \|\nabla f_{k+1} + G_{k+1}^T \lambda_{k+1}^{\star \text{true}}\| \right) \\ &\leq \sum_{k=m_i}^{n_i-1} \|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}} - \nabla f_{k+1} - G_{k+1}^T \lambda_{k+1}^{\star \text{true}}\| \\ &\leq \sum_{k=m_i}^{n_i-1} (\|\nabla f_k - \nabla f_{k+1}\| + \|G_k - G_{k+1}\| \|\lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\| + \|G_{k+1}\| \|\lambda_k^{\star \text{true}} - \lambda_{k+1}^{\star \text{true}}\|) \\ &\stackrel{(18)}{\leq} \Upsilon \sum_{k=m_i}^{n_i-1} \left(\frac{\nu-1}{\kappa \nabla c} \alpha_k + \psi \alpha_k^p \right), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{F.21})$$

where the existence of Υ in the last inequality is due to the same analysis as in (F.6) (note that \bar{g}_k is bounded for any particular run due to Lemma 1 and boundedness of ∇f_k in Assumption 1). Multiplying both sides of (F.21) by $(\epsilon^*)^2$, we have

$$(\epsilon^*)^3 \stackrel{(\text{F.20})}{\leq} \Upsilon \sum_{k=m_i}^{n_i-1} \left(\frac{\nu-1}{\kappa \nabla c} \alpha_k + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\|^2,$$

which implies that

$$\infty \leq \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \sum_{k=m_i}^{n_i-1} \left(\frac{\nu-1}{\kappa \nabla c} \alpha_k + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\|^2 \leq \sum_{k=K^*}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\nu-1}{\kappa \nabla c} \alpha_k + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\|^2 \stackrel{(\text{F.19})}{<} \infty.$$

Here, the last inequality also uses the fact that $p \geq 1$. This leads to a contradiction. Thus, we obtain $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}\| + \|c_k\| = 0$ almost surely. By Lemma 1 and the definitions of $\lambda_k^{\star \text{true}}$ and λ_k^* , we have $\lambda_k^{\star \text{true}} - \lambda_k^* \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely, which implies $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \|\nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k^*\| + \|c_k\| = 0$ almost surely. This completes the proof.

G. Proofs of Section 4

G.1. Proof of Lemma 5

Recall from the proof of Theorem 1 that $\lambda_k^{\text{sub}} := \lambda_k + \Delta\lambda_k$, where we use $(\Delta\mathbf{x}_k, \Delta\lambda_k)$ to denote the solution of (13) but with $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k$ replaced by ∇f_k and \tilde{G}_k replaced by G_k . Let us define $\tilde{\lambda}_k^{\text{sub}} = \lambda_k + \tilde{\Delta}\lambda_k$. By the proof of Lemma 4, we know for any run of the algorithm, there exists a (potentially random) $K^* < \infty$ such that $(\Delta\mathbf{x}_k, \Delta\lambda_k)$ is well-defined (note that Lemma 1 is applicable since (23) implies (20)). By (13), we note for $k \geq K^*$ that

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{B}_k & G_k^T \\ G_k & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\mathbf{x}_k \\ \lambda_k^{\text{sub}} \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f_k \\ c_k \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{B}_k & (G^*)^T \\ G^* & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \lambda^* \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f^* \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\mathbf{x}_k \\ \lambda_k^{\text{sub}} - \lambda^* \end{pmatrix} \right\| &= \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{B}_k & G_k^T \\ G_k & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f_k \\ c_k \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{B}_k & (G^*)^T \\ G^* & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f^* \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\| \\ &\stackrel{\text{(E.15)}}{\leq} \Upsilon_K \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f_k - \nabla f^* \\ c_k \end{pmatrix} \right\| + \Upsilon_K^2 \|\nabla f^*\| \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} & G_k^T - (G^*)^T \\ G_k - G^* & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\| \\ &\leq \Upsilon_K (\kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_c) \|\mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}^*\| + 2\Upsilon_K^2 \Upsilon_{\nabla f} \kappa_{\nabla c} \|\mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}^*\|, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.1})$$

where in the last inequality, $\kappa_{\nabla f}, \kappa_{\nabla c}$ denote the Lipschitz constants of ∇f and $G = \nabla c$; $\Upsilon_{\nabla f}$ is the upper bound of ∇f over \mathcal{X} (cf. Appendix F.2); and we abuse the notation κ_c from Assumption 1 to denote the Lipschitz constant of c over \mathcal{X} . Note that κ_c always exists since c has bounded Jacobian as assumed in Assumption 1. Thus, we have from (G.1) that $\lambda_k^{\text{sub}} \rightarrow \lambda^*$ almost surely. Then, we characterize $\lambda_k^{\text{sub}} - \tilde{\lambda}_k^{\text{sub}}$. We have from (13) that

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{B}_k & \tilde{G}_k^T \\ \tilde{G}_k & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k \\ \tilde{\Delta}\lambda_k \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k + \tilde{G}_k^T \lambda_k \\ c_k \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{B}_k & G_k^T \\ G_k & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Delta\mathbf{x}_k \\ \Delta\lambda_k \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{pmatrix} \nabla f_k + G_k^T \lambda_k \\ c_k \end{pmatrix}.$$

Following the same derivations as in (G.1) and applying Lemma 1, we immediately obtain $\|(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k - \Delta\mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\Delta}\lambda_k - \Delta\lambda_k)\| \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely; thus $\|\lambda_k^{\text{sub}} - \tilde{\lambda}_k^{\text{sub}}\| \rightarrow 0$. Combining the above convergence results, we know $\tilde{\lambda}_k^{\text{sub}} \rightarrow \lambda^*$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. Finally, for any run of the algorithm and any $\epsilon > 0$, we abuse the notation K^* to let $\bar{\alpha}_k \leq 1$ and $\|\tilde{\lambda}_k^{\text{sub}} - \lambda^*\| \leq \epsilon$ for $k \geq K^*$. Then, we know that, for any $k \geq K^*$,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\| &= \|\lambda_k - \lambda^* + \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{\Delta}\lambda_k\| \leq (1 - \bar{\alpha}_k) \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| + \bar{\alpha}_k \|\tilde{\lambda}_k^{\text{sub}} - \lambda^*\| \\ &\leq \prod_{j=K^*}^k (1 - \bar{\alpha}_j) \|\lambda_{K^*} - \lambda^*\| + \sum_{i=K^*}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \bar{\alpha}_j) \bar{\alpha}_i \|\tilde{\lambda}_i^{\text{sub}} - \lambda^*\| \\ &\leq \prod_{j=K^*}^k (1 - \bar{\alpha}_j) \|\lambda_{K^*} - \lambda^*\| + \epsilon \sum_{i=K^*}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \bar{\alpha}_j) \bar{\alpha}_i \\ &= \prod_{j=K^*}^k (1 - \bar{\alpha}_j) \|\lambda_{K^*} - \lambda^*\| + \epsilon \left\{ 1 - \prod_{j=K^*}^k (1 - \bar{\alpha}_j) \right\} \\ &\leq \|\lambda_{K^*} - \lambda^*\| \exp\left(-\sum_{j=K^*}^k \bar{\alpha}_j\right) + \epsilon, \end{aligned}$$

where the third inequality is due to the second inequality and induction. Noting that $\sum_{j=K^*}^{\infty} \bar{\alpha}_j = \infty$ as $p_1 \leq 1$, we know there exists $K^{**} \geq K^*$ such that $\|\lambda_{K^*} - \lambda^*\| \exp(-\sum_{j=K^*}^k \bar{\alpha}_j) \leq \epsilon$ for all $k \geq K^{**}$. This implies that $\|\lambda_{k+1} - \lambda^*\| \leq 2\epsilon$ for all $k \geq K^{**}$ and we complete the proof.

G.2. Proof of Lemma 6

We note that by (11),

$$\tilde{B}_k = \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i \widehat{\nabla}_x^2 \mathcal{L}_i + \prod_{i=0}^k (1 - \beta_i) \tilde{B}_{-1}.$$

Without loss of generality, we suppose $\beta_k \leq 1$ for all $k \geq 0$ (otherwise, we just consider k large enough). We obtain from the above display that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \|\bar{B}_k - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^*\| &= \left\| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\widehat{\nabla}_x^2 \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^*) + \prod_{i=0}^k (1 - \beta_i) (\bar{B}_{-1} - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^*) \right\| \\
 &\leq \left\| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\widehat{\nabla}_x^2 \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}_i) \right\| + \left\| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^*) \right\| \\
 &\quad + \prod_{i=0}^k (1 - \beta_i) \|\bar{B}_{-1} - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^*\| \\
 &\leq \left\| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]) \right\| \\
 &\quad + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i \cdot \|\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] - \nabla^2 f_i\| \\
 &\quad + \sum_{l=1}^m \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i \cdot |\lambda_i^l - (\lambda^*)^l| \cdot \|\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l - \nabla^2 c_i^l\| \\
 &\quad + \sum_{l=1}^m |(\lambda^*)^l| \cdot \left\| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]) \right\| \\
 &\quad + \sum_{l=1}^m |(\lambda^*)^l| \cdot \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i \cdot \|\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] - \nabla^2 c_i^l\| \\
 &\quad + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i \|\nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^*\| + \prod_{i=0}^k (1 - \beta_i) \|\bar{B}_{-1} - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^*\| \\
 &=: \mathcal{I}_1^k + \mathcal{I}_2^k + \mathcal{I}_3^k + \mathcal{I}_4^k + \mathcal{I}_5^k + \mathcal{I}_6^k + \mathcal{I}_7^k. \tag{G.2}
 \end{aligned}$$

We analyze each term separately. We first present a generic result. For any sequence $e_i \rightarrow 0$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$, we have $\sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i e_i \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ as long as $\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \beta_i = \infty$ (as implied by (24)). In fact, for any $\epsilon > 0$, there exists $i' > 0$ such that $|e_i| \leq \epsilon$ for any $i \geq i'$. Thus, for $k \geq i'$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \left| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i e_i \right| &\leq \sum_{i=0}^{i'-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i |e_i| + \sum_{i=i'}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i |e_i| \\
 &\leq \prod_{j=i'}^k (1 - \beta_j) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{i'-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{i'-1} (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i |e_i| + \epsilon \sum_{i=i'}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i \\
 &= \prod_{j=i'}^k (1 - \beta_j) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{i'-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{i'-1} (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i |e_i| + \epsilon \left\{ 1 - \prod_{j=i'}^k (1 - \beta_j) \right\} \\
 &\leq \exp\left(-\sum_{j=i'}^k \beta_j\right) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{i'-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{i'-1} (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i |e_i| + \epsilon.
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \beta_i = \infty$, we can find $k' \geq i'$ large enough such that $\exp(-\sum_{j=i'}^k \beta_j) \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{i'-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{i'-1} (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i |e_i| \leq \epsilon$ for any $k \geq k'$. Then, we obtain for $k \geq k'$ that

$$\left| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i e_i \right| \leq 2\epsilon.$$

This shows $\sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \beta_i e_i \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. With this argument, we study each term as follows.

- For I_2^k, I_5^k, I_6^k , we know from Lemmas 11 and 5 that $\|\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] - \nabla^2 f_i\| \rightarrow 0$, $\|\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] - \nabla^2 c_i^l\| \rightarrow 0$, $\forall 1 \leq l \leq m$, and $\nabla_{\mathbf{x}}^2 \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla_{\mathbf{x}}^2 \mathcal{L}^* \rightarrow 0$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely (where we use the conditions $p_3 > 0$ and $2p_4 - p_3 > 0$ from (24)). Thus, $I_2^k, I_5^k, I_6^k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely.
- For I_7^k , we have $\prod_{i=0}^k (1-\beta_i) \leq \exp(-\sum_{i=0}^k \beta_i) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, $I_7^k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$.
- For I_3^k , we provide a deterministic upper bound on $\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l$ for any $1 \leq l \leq m$. In particular, we note from the definition (7) that

$$\begin{aligned} \widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l &= \frac{\{c^l(\mathbf{x}_i + b_i \Delta_i + \widetilde{b}_i \widetilde{\Delta}_i) - c^l(\mathbf{x}_i + b_i \Delta_i)\} - \{c^l(\mathbf{x}_i - b_i \Delta_i + \widetilde{b}_i \widetilde{\Delta}_i) - c^l(\mathbf{x}_i - b_i \Delta_i)\}}{2b_i \widetilde{b}_i} \\ &\quad \times \frac{\Delta_i^{-1} \widetilde{\Delta}_i^{-T} + \widetilde{\Delta}_i^{-1} \Delta_i^{-T}}{2} \\ &= \frac{1}{2b_i \widetilde{b}_i} \int_0^{\widetilde{b}_i} \int_{-b_i}^{b_i} \Delta_i^T \nabla^2 c^l(\mathbf{x}_i + s_1 \Delta_i + s_2 \widetilde{\Delta}_i) \widetilde{\Delta}_i ds_1 ds_2 \times \frac{\Delta_i^{-1} \widetilde{\Delta}_i^{-T} + \widetilde{\Delta}_i^{-1} \Delta_i^{-T}}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.3})$$

By the boundedness of $\nabla^2 c^l$ over \mathcal{X} and Assumption 3, we know there exists a deterministic constant $Y_{\widehat{\nabla}^2 c} > 0$ such that $\|\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l\| \leq Y_{\widehat{\nabla}^2 c}$ for any $i \geq 0$ and $1 \leq l \leq m$. With this boundedness property and the fact that $\lambda_i^l - (\lambda^*)^l \rightarrow 0$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$, we know $I_3^k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely.

- For I_4^k , we apply Lemma 9 and have

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j)^2 \beta_i^2 \mathbb{E}[\|\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_i^l | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]\|^2 | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] = O(\beta_k) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow \infty. \quad (\text{G.4})$$

Thus, the martingale convergence theorem (Hall and Heyde 2014, Theorem 2.18) implies that $I_4^k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely.

- For I_1^k , based on Assumption 6, let us fix any $0 < \delta' < \delta$ and let $K' > 0$ be a deterministic index such that for any $\mathbf{x} \in \{\mathbf{x} : \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*\| \leq \delta'\}$ and for all $k \geq K'$, we have $\mathbf{x} + s_1 \Delta + s_2 \widetilde{\Delta} \in \{\mathbf{x} : \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*\| \leq \delta\}$ for any $s_1 \in [-b_k, b_k]$, $s_2 \in [0, \widetilde{b}_k]$, and $\Delta, \widetilde{\Delta} \sim \mathcal{P}_\Delta$. Note that such a K' must exist due to Assumption 3 and the fact that $b_k, \widetilde{b}_k \rightarrow 0$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} I_1^k &= \left\| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \beta_i (\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]) \right\| \\ &\leq \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \beta_i \|\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]\| \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}^*\| > \delta'} \\ &\quad + \prod_{j=K'}^k (1-\beta_j) \sum_{i=0}^{K'-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{K'-1} (1-\beta_j) \beta_i \|\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]\| \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}^*\| \leq \delta'} \\ &\quad + \left\| \sum_{i=K'}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \beta_i (\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]) \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}^*\| \leq \delta'} \right\|. \end{aligned}$$

The first term on the right-hand side converges to zero almost surely since $\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}^* \rightarrow 0$ as $i \rightarrow \infty$. The second term converges to zero almost surely since $\prod_{j=K'}^k (1-\beta_j) \leq \exp(-\sum_{j=K'}^k \beta_j) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. The third term also converges to zero almost surely by following the same derivation as in (G.3) and applying Assumption 6 to show that $\mathbb{E}[\|\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i)\|^2 | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]$ is bounded for $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{X} \cap \{\mathbf{x} : \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*\| \leq \delta'\}$, thereby obtaining (G.4), and then applying the martingale convergence theorem (Hall and Heyde 2014, Theorem 2.18). Thus, we conclude that $I_1^k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely.

Combining the above arguments of $I_1^k, I_2^k, I_3^k, I_4^k, I_5^k, I_6^k, I_7^k$ and plugging into (G.2), we have shown that $\bar{B}_k \rightarrow \nabla_{\mathbf{x}}^2 \mathcal{L}^*$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. For the second part of the statement, for each run of the algorithm with k large enough, we know $\|\bar{B}_k\| \leq \kappa_{1, \bar{B}}$. In addition, we let $\bar{Z}_k, Z^* \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times (d-m)}$ be the matrices whose columns are orthonormal and

span the spaces of $\ker(\tilde{G}_k)$, $\ker(G^*)$, respectively. Then, by Davis-Kahan $\sin(\theta)$ theorem (Davis and Kahan 1970, Pensky 2024) and Lemma 1, we know

$$\inf_{Q \in Q_{d-m}} \|\tilde{Z}_k - Z^*Q\| \leq 2\sqrt{2}\|\tilde{Z}_k\tilde{Z}_k^T - Z^*(Z^*)^T\| = \|\tilde{G}_k^T(\tilde{G}_k\tilde{G}_k^T)^{-1}\tilde{G}_k - (G^*)^T(G^*(G^*)^T)^{-1}G^*\| \rightarrow 0,$$

where Q_{d-m} denotes the set of $(d-m) \times (d-m)$ orthonormal matrices. Thus, we obtain

$$\lambda_{\min}(\tilde{Z}_k^T\tilde{B}_k\tilde{Z}_k) = \lambda_{\min}(Q\tilde{Z}_k^T\tilde{B}_k\tilde{Z}_kQ^T) \rightarrow \lambda_{\min}((Z^*)^T\nabla_x^2\mathcal{L}^*Z^*),$$

which implies $\lambda_{\min}(\tilde{Z}_k^T\tilde{B}_k\tilde{Z}_k) \geq \kappa_{1,\tilde{B}}$ for large enough k . This completes the proof.

G.3. Proof of Lemma 7

To simplify the notation, we will just fix $\epsilon \in (0, 1 - 0.5/(\zeta\iota_1)\mathbf{1}_{p_1=1})$ and denote $\tau_{k_0} = \tau_{k_0}(\epsilon)$. We use Y_1, Y_2, \dots to denote generic deterministic constants and may also use $O(\cdot)$ to ignore them. However, when they depend on k_0 , we denote by $Y_i(k_0)$ for clarification and do not write $O(\cdot)$. In what follows, we suppose k_0 is large enough (threshold index is deterministic) such that

$$\frac{\nu-1}{\kappa\nabla_c}\alpha_k + \psi\alpha_k^p \leq 0.5\epsilon^5 \quad \forall k \geq k_0. \quad (\text{G.5})$$

To prove Lemma 7, we need two lemmas, which are proved in Appendices G.4 and G.5.

LEMMA 14. *Under the conditions of Lemma 7 and suppose (G.5), there exist constants $Y_1, Y_2(k_0) > 0$ such that for any $k \geq k_0$,*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\left[\|\mathbf{z}_{k+1}\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k+1}\right] &\leq \mathbb{E}\left[\{1 - 2(1-\epsilon)\bar{\alpha}_k\}\|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k+1}\right] + Y_1\alpha_k\mathbb{E}\left[\|\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k - \nabla\mathcal{L}_k\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k}\right], \\ \mathbb{E}\left[\|\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_{k+1} - \nabla\mathcal{L}_{k+1}\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k+1}\right] &\leq Y_1(\beta_k + b_k^4) + Y_2(k_0)\exp\left(-\frac{2\iota_2k^{1-p_2}}{1-p_2}\right) \\ &\quad + Y_1\left(\sum_{i=k_0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j)\alpha_i \left\{\mathbb{E}[(\|\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_i - \nabla\mathcal{L}_i\|^2 + \|\mathbf{z}_i\|^2)\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>i}]\right\}^{1/2}\right)^2. \end{aligned}$$

LEMMA 15. *Under the conditions of Lemma 7, for any $q \geq 0$, there exists a deterministic integer $\bar{k}_0 > 0$ such that for any $k_0 \geq \bar{k}_0$, there exists a constant $Y_3(k_0)$ such that*

$$\max\left\{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k}], \mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k - \nabla\mathcal{L}_k\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k}]\right\} \leq Y_3(k_0)\left(\beta_k + b_k^4 + (\alpha_k/\beta_k)^{2q}\right) \quad \text{for any } k \geq k_0.$$

By Lemma 15, we choose q large enough such that $2q(p_1 - p_2) > \min\{p_2, 4p_3\}$. Then, we have $(\alpha_k/\beta_k)^{2q} = o(\beta_k + b_k^4)$. This completes the proof.

G.4. Proof of Lemma 14

By Algorithm 1, we know for any fixed $\epsilon \in (0, 1 - 0.5/(\zeta\iota_1)\mathbf{1}_{p_1=1})$ and $k \geq k_0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{z}_{k+1}\|^2 &= \|\mathbf{z}_k + \bar{\alpha}_k(\tilde{\Delta}\mathbf{x}_k, \tilde{\Delta}\lambda_k)\|^2 = \|\mathbf{z}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k\|^2 = \|\mathbf{z}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\nabla\mathcal{L}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k\tilde{W}_k^{-1}(\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k - \nabla\mathcal{L}_k)\|^2 \\ &= \|\mathbf{z}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\nabla\mathcal{L}_k\|^2 + \bar{\alpha}_k^2\|\tilde{W}_k^{-1}(\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k - \nabla\mathcal{L}_k)\|^2 - 2\bar{\alpha}_k\langle\mathbf{z}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\nabla\mathcal{L}_k, \tilde{W}_k^{-1}(\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k - \nabla\mathcal{L}_k)\rangle \\ &\leq (1 + \epsilon\bar{\alpha}_k)\|\mathbf{z}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\nabla\mathcal{L}_k\|^2 + (\bar{\alpha}_k^2 + \bar{\alpha}_k/\epsilon)\|\tilde{W}_k^{-1}(\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k - \nabla\mathcal{L}_k)\|^2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.6})$$

For the second term on the right-hand side, we apply the definition of τ_{k_0} in (25) and have

$$\|\tilde{W}_k^{-1}(\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k - \nabla\mathcal{L}_k)\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k+1} \leq \|\tilde{W}_k^{-1}(\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k - \nabla\mathcal{L}_k)\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k} \leq \frac{\|\bar{\nabla}\mathcal{L}_k - \nabla\mathcal{L}_k\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k}}{\epsilon^2}. \quad (\text{G.7})$$

For the first term on the right-hand side, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathbf{z}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\nabla\mathcal{L}_k\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k+1} &= (\|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 - 2\bar{\alpha}_k\langle\mathbf{z}_k, \tilde{W}_k^{-1}\nabla\mathcal{L}_k\rangle + \bar{\alpha}_k^2\|\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\nabla\mathcal{L}_k\|^2)\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k+1} \\ &= (1 - 2\bar{\alpha}_k)\|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k+1} + \bar{\alpha}_k(2\langle\mathbf{z}_k, \mathbf{z}_k - \tilde{W}_k^{-1}\nabla\mathcal{L}_k\rangle + \bar{\alpha}_k\|\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\nabla\mathcal{L}_k\|^2)\mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0}>k+1} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\stackrel{(25)}{\leq} (1 - 2\bar{\alpha}_k) \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} + \bar{\alpha}_k \left(\frac{2}{\epsilon} \|\mathbf{z}_k\| \|\nabla \mathcal{L}_k - \bar{W}_k \mathbf{z}_k\| + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_k}{\epsilon^2} \|\nabla \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \right) \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \\
&\stackrel{(25)}{\leq} (1 - 2\bar{\alpha}_k) \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} + \bar{\alpha}_k \left(0.5\epsilon \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_k}{\epsilon^4} \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \right) \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \\
&\stackrel{(G.5)}{\leq} (1 - (2 - \epsilon)\bar{\alpha}_k) \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1}. \tag{G.8}
\end{aligned}$$

Combining (G.6), (G.7), (G.8) and applying (G.5), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\mathbf{z}_{k+1}\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} &\leq (1 + \epsilon\bar{\alpha}_k)(1 - (2 - \epsilon)\bar{\alpha}_k) \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} + \left(0.5\epsilon^3 + \frac{1}{\epsilon^3} \right) \bar{\alpha}_k \|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\
&\stackrel{(18)}{\leq} \{1 - 2(1 - \epsilon)\bar{\alpha}_k\} \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} + \left(0.5\epsilon^3 + \frac{1}{\epsilon^3} \right) \left(\frac{\nu-1}{\kappa\nabla c} \alpha_k + \psi \alpha_k^p \right) \|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k}.
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the first part of the result by taking expectation on both sides and setting Υ_1 large enough. For the second part of the result, we apply (25) and note that, for $k_0 \leq k < \tau_{k_0} - 1$,

$$\begin{aligned}
&\bar{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_{k+1} - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}_{k+1} \\
&= \bar{\mathbf{g}}_{k+1} - \nabla f_{k+1} + (\bar{G}_{k+1} - G_{k+1})^T \lambda_{k+1} = \bar{\mathbf{g}}_{k+1} - \nabla f_{k+1} + (\bar{G}_{k+1} - G_{k+1})^T \lambda_{k+1} \\
&\stackrel{(5)}{=} \beta_{k+1} (\bar{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_{k+1}; \xi_{k+1}) - \nabla f_{k+1}) + (1 - \beta_{k+1})(\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k - \nabla f_k) + (1 - \beta_{k+1})(\nabla f_k - \nabla f_{k+1}) \\
&\quad + \left\{ \beta_{k+1} (\bar{\nabla} c_{k+1} - G_{k+1}) + (1 - \beta_{k+1})(\bar{G}_k - G_k) + (1 - \beta_{k+1})(G_k - G_{k+1}) \right\}^T \lambda_{k+1} \\
&\stackrel{(E.11)}{=} \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i \left(\bar{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\bar{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] \right) \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i \left(\mathbb{E}[\bar{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] - \nabla f_i \right) + \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j) (\nabla f_{i-1} - \nabla f_i) \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\bar{\nabla} c_i - \mathbb{E}[\bar{\nabla} c_i | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}])^T \lambda_{k+1} + \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i (\mathbb{E}[\bar{\nabla} c_i | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}] - G_i)^T \lambda_{k+1} \\
&\quad + \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j) (G_{i-1} - G_i)^T \lambda_{k+1} =: \mathcal{J}_1^k + \mathcal{J}_2^k + \mathcal{J}_3^k + \mathcal{J}_4^k + \mathcal{J}_5^k + \mathcal{J}_6^k. \tag{G.9}
\end{aligned}$$

We provide the upper bounds for the terms $\mathcal{J}_1^k, \mathcal{J}_2^k, \mathcal{J}_3^k$, while the terms $\mathcal{J}_4^k, \mathcal{J}_5^k, \mathcal{J}_6^k$ can be proved in the same way by noting that $\|\lambda_{k+1}\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \leq 1/\epsilon$. For \mathcal{J}_1^k , we apply Lemma 9 and have

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E}[\|\mathcal{J}_1^k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1}] &\leq \mathbb{E}[\|\mathcal{J}_1^k\|^2] = \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j)^2 \beta_i^2 \mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) - \mathbb{E}[\bar{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_i; \xi_i) | \mathcal{F}_{i-1}]\|^2] \\
&\stackrel{(F.5)}{\leq} \mathcal{O} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j)^2 \beta_i^2 \right) = \mathcal{O}(\beta_k). \tag{G.10}
\end{aligned}$$

For \mathcal{J}_2^k , we apply Lemmas 11 and 9 and have

$$\mathbb{E}[\|\mathcal{J}_2^k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1}] \leq \mathbb{E}[\|\mathcal{J}_2^k\|^2] = \mathcal{O} \left(\left(\sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j) \beta_i b_i^2 \right)^2 \right) = \mathcal{O}(b_k^4). \tag{G.11}$$

For \mathcal{J}_3^k , we have

$$\|\mathcal{J}_3^k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \leq \left\| \sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i}^{k+1} (1 - \beta_j) (\nabla f_{i-1} - \nabla f_i) \right\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\stackrel{\text{(F.6)}}{\leq} \kappa_{\nabla f}^2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i}^{k+1} (1-\beta_j) \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{i-1}\| \right)^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \quad (\text{Lipschitz continuity}) \\
 &= \kappa_{\nabla f}^2 \left(\sum_{i=0}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i}^{k+1} (1-\beta_j) \bar{\alpha}_{i-1} \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_{i-1}\| \right)^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1}. \tag{G.12}
 \end{aligned}$$

We separate the sum on the right-hand side into two parts, $i = 0$ to k_0 and $i = k_0 + 1$ to $k + 1$. In particular, for the first part, there exists a constant $\Upsilon_2(k_0) > 0$ depending on k_0 such that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathbb{E} \left[\left(\sum_{i=0}^{k_0} \prod_{j=i}^{k+1} (1-\beta_j) \bar{\alpha}_{i-1} \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_{i-1}\| \right)^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] \stackrel{\text{(F.10)}}{\leq} \Upsilon_2(k_0) \prod_{j=k_0}^{k+1} (1-\beta_j)^2 \leq \Upsilon_2(k_0) \exp \left(-2 \sum_{j=k_0}^{k+1} \beta_j \right) \\
 &\leq \Upsilon_2(k_0) \exp \left(- \int_{k_0}^{k+2} \frac{2t_2}{(j+1)^{p_2}} dj \right) \leq \Upsilon_2(k_0) \exp \left(\frac{2t_2(k_0+1)^{1-p_2}}{1-p_2} \right) \exp \left(- \frac{2t_2 k^{1-p_2}}{1-p_2} \right). \tag{G.13}
 \end{aligned}$$

For the second part, there exists a constant $\Upsilon_3 > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathbb{E} \left[\left(\sum_{i=k_0+1}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i}^{k+1} (1-\beta_j) \bar{\alpha}_{i-1} \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_{i-1}\| \right)^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] = \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\sum_{i=k_0+1}^{k+1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k+1} (1-\beta_j) \bar{\alpha}_i \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_i\| \right)^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] \\
 &\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\sum_{i=k_0+1}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \bar{\alpha}_i \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_i\| \right)^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] \stackrel{\text{(18)}}{\leq} \frac{\Upsilon_3}{\epsilon^2} \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\sum_{i=k_0+1}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \alpha_i \|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_i\| \right)^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] \\
 &\leq \frac{\Upsilon_3}{\epsilon^2} \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\sum_{i=k_0+1}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \alpha_i \|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_i\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > i} \right)^2 \right] \leq \frac{\Upsilon_3}{\epsilon^2} \left(\sum_{i=k_0+1}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \alpha_i \left\{ \mathbb{E} [\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_i\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > i}] \right\}^{1/2} \right)^2 \\
 &\leq \frac{2\Upsilon_3}{\epsilon^2} \left(\sum_{i=k_0+1}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \alpha_i \left\{ \mathbb{E} [(\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla \mathcal{L}_i\|^2 + \|\nabla \mathcal{L}_i\|^2) \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > i}] \right\}^{1/2} \right)^2 \\
 &\stackrel{\text{(25)}}{\leq} \frac{2\Upsilon_3}{\epsilon^4} \left(\sum_{i=k_0+1}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1-\beta_j) \alpha_i \left\{ \mathbb{E} [(\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla \mathcal{L}_i\|^2 + \|\mathbf{z}_i\|^2) \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > i}] \right\}^{1/2} \right)^2. \tag{G.14}
 \end{aligned}$$

Combining (G.9), (G.10), (G.11), (G.12), (G.13), (G.14), and noting that $\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_{k+1} - \nabla \mathcal{L}_{k+1}\| = \|\bar{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_{k+1} - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}_{k+1}\|$, we complete the proof of the second part of the result.

G.5. Proof of Lemma 15

We prove the statement by induction. Recall that $\epsilon \in (0, 1 - 0.5/(\zeta t_1) \mathbf{1}_{p_1=1})$ is fixed and we denote $\tau_{k_0} = \tau_{k_0}(\epsilon)$. We have $\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k}] \leq \epsilon^4$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] &= \mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] \\
 &\leq 2 \left(\mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\|\nabla_x \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] \right) \stackrel{\text{(25)}}{\leq} 2 \left(\mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] + \epsilon^2 \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, to prove the result for $q = 0$, it suffices to show $\mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k}]$ is upper bounded. In fact, we note that

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] = \mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k + \bar{\mathbf{G}}_k^T \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] \leq 2 \left(\mathbb{E} [\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\|^2] + \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \mathbb{E} [\|\bar{\mathbf{G}}_k\|^2] \right).$$

By (F.9) we know $\mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{g}}_k\|^2] \leq \Upsilon_{\bar{\mathbf{g}}}$ for all $k \geq 0$ while the term $\mathbb{E}[\|\bar{\mathbf{G}}_k\|^2]$ can be proved in the same way. Thus, combining the above two displays, we know the result holds for $q = 0$. Suppose the result holds for $q \geq 0$, we aim to establish the result for $q + 1$. We apply Lemma 14 and obtain for some constants $\Upsilon_1(k_0), \Upsilon_2(k_0), \Upsilon_3(k_0) > 0$ that for any $k \geq k_0$,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_{k+1} - \nabla \mathcal{L}_{k+1}\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq Y_1(k_0) \left(\beta_k + b_k^4 + \left\{ \sum_{i=k_0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \alpha_i \left(\sqrt{\beta_i} + b_i^2 + \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{\beta_i} \right)^q \right) \right\}^2 \right) \\
&\leq Y_1(k_0) \left(\beta_k + b_k^4 + \left\{ \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \beta_j) \alpha_i \left(\sqrt{\beta_i} + b_i^2 + \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{\beta_i} \right)^q \right) \right\}^2 \right) \\
&\leq Y_2(k_0) \left(\beta_k + b_k^4 + \frac{\alpha_k^2}{\beta_k^2} \left\{ \beta_k + b_k^4 + \left(\frac{\alpha_k}{\beta_k} \right)^{2q} \right\} \right) \quad (\text{Lemma 9}) \\
&\leq Y_3(k_0) \left(\beta_k + b_k^4 + (\alpha_k/\beta_k)^{2(q+1)} \right). \tag{G.15}
\end{aligned}$$

In addition, by Lemma 14, we also have for some constant $Y_4 > 0$ such that for any $k \geq k_0$,

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} \left[\|\mathbf{z}_{k+1}\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] \\
&\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\{1 - 2(1 - \epsilon)\bar{\alpha}_k\} \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] + Y_4 \alpha_k \mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] \\
&\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\left\{ 1 - \frac{2(1 - \epsilon)\nu_k \alpha_k}{\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}} \right\} \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] + Y_4 \alpha_k \mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] \\
&\leq \{1 - 2(1 - \epsilon)\zeta \alpha_k\} \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right] + Y_4 \alpha_k \mathbb{E} \left[\|\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \right],
\end{aligned}$$

where the last inequality uses the fact that $2(1 - \epsilon)\zeta \alpha_k < 1$ (it holds for k large enough with deterministic threshold index). Applying the above inequality recursively with the bound in (G.15), we know for some constant $Y_5(k_0) > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbb{E} \left[\|\mathbf{z}_{k+1}\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] &\leq Y_5(k_0) \sum_{i=k_0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k \{1 - 2\zeta(1 - \epsilon)\alpha_j\} \alpha_i \left(\beta_i + b_i^4 + \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{\beta_i} \right)^{2(q+1)} \right) \\
&\leq Y_5(k_0) \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k \{1 - 2\zeta(1 - \epsilon)\alpha_j\} \alpha_i \left(\beta_i + b_i^4 + \left(\frac{\alpha_i}{\beta_i} \right)^{2(q+1)} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 9 and the condition $2\zeta\alpha_1(1 - \epsilon) > 1$ when $p_1 = 1$, we know

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k \{1 - 2\zeta(1 - \epsilon)\alpha_j\} \alpha_i \beta_i = O(\beta_k).$$

Without loss of generality, we suppose $\beta_k = o(b_k^4 + (\alpha_k/\beta_k)^{2(q+1)})$; otherwise the result is trivial. Then, Lemma 9 also leads to

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k \{1 - 2\zeta(1 - \epsilon)\alpha_j\} \alpha_i \left(b_i^4 + (\alpha_i/\beta_i)^{2(q+1)} \right) = O \left(b_k^4 + (\alpha_k/\beta_k)^{2(q+1)} \right).$$

Combining the above three displays, we obtain

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\|\tilde{\mathbf{z}}_{k+1}\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k+1} \right] \leq Y_6(k_0) \left(\beta_k + b_k^4 + (\alpha_k/\beta_k)^{2(q+1)} \right). \tag{G.16}$$

Combining (G.15) and (G.16), we prove that the result holds for $q + 1$. This completes the induction step and concludes the proof.

G.6. Proof of Lemma 13

For notational conciseness, we follow Appendix G.3 and use Y_1, Y_2, \dots to denote generic deterministic constants. We note that

$$\begin{aligned}
\|\tilde{W}_k - W^*\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} &\stackrel{(13),(25)}{=} \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \bar{B}_k - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}^* & (\bar{G}_k - G^*)^T \\ \bar{G}_k - G^* & \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\
&\leq 2\|\bar{B}_k - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}^*\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} + 2\|\bar{G}_k - G^*\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k}. \tag{G.17}
\end{aligned}$$

We bound $\|\bar{B}_k - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}^*\|^2$ as an example, while the bound of $\|\bar{G}_k - G^*\|^2$ can be derived in the same way with only fewer terms, resulting in the same upper bound. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{B}_k &= (1 - \beta_k)\bar{B}_{k-1} + \beta_k \widehat{\nabla}_x^2 \mathcal{L}_k = (1 - \beta_k)\bar{B}_{k-1} + \beta_k \left(\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) + \sum_{j=1}^m \lambda_k^j \widehat{\nabla}^2 c_k^j \right) \\ &= \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left(\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) + \sum_{j=1}^m \lambda_h^j \widehat{\nabla}^2 c_h^j \right) + \prod_{h=0}^k (1 - \beta_h) \bar{B}_{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

With the above expression, we have a similar decomposition to (G.2) and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{B}_k - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^* &= \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left(\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \right) \\ &+ \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left(\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] - \nabla^2 f_h \right) + \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (\nabla^2 f_h - \nabla^2 f^*) \\ &+ \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left(\sum_{j=1}^m \lambda_h^j - (\lambda^*)^j \right) \widehat{\nabla}^2 c_h^j + \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \sum_{j=1}^m (\lambda^*)^j \left(\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_h^j - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_h^j | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \right) \\ &+ \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \sum_{j=1}^m (\lambda^*)^j \left(\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 c_h^j | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] - \nabla^2 c_h^j \right) + \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \sum_{j=1}^m (\lambda^*)^j \left(\nabla^2 c_h^j - (\nabla^2 c^j)^* \right) \\ &+ \prod_{h=0}^k (1 - \beta_h) (\bar{B}_{-1} - \nabla_x^2 \mathcal{L}^*) =: \mathcal{K}_1^k + \mathcal{K}_2^k + \mathcal{K}_3^k + \mathcal{K}_4^k + \mathcal{K}_5^k + \mathcal{K}_6^k + \mathcal{K}_7^k + \mathcal{K}_8^k. \end{aligned}$$

We establish the bounds for $\mathcal{K}_1^k, \mathcal{K}_2^k, \mathcal{K}_3^k, \mathcal{K}_4^k$, while the bounds of $\mathcal{K}_5^k, \mathcal{K}_6^k, \mathcal{K}_7^k$ can be derived similarly to those of $\mathcal{K}_1^k, \mathcal{K}_2^k, \mathcal{K}_3^k$, and $\|\mathcal{K}_8^k\|^2 = O(\prod_{h=0}^k (1 - \beta_h)^2) \leq \exp(-2 \sum_{h=0}^k \beta_h) = o(\beta_k)$ by (G.13) only contributes to the higher-order error.

• For \mathcal{K}_1^k , we know from the proof of Lemma 6 in Appendix G.2 that there exist $0 < \delta' < \delta$, a deterministic threshold $K' > 0$, and a constant $\Upsilon_1 > 0$ such that for any $k \geq K'$ and any $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathcal{X}_{\delta'}$:= $\mathcal{X} \cap \{\mathbf{x} : \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*\| \leq \delta'\}$, we have $\mathbb{E}[\|\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_k; \xi_k) | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}]\|] \leq \Upsilon_1$. With this property, we separate \mathcal{K}_1^k into three terms:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{K}_1^k &= \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left(\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \right) \mathbf{1}_{\mathbf{x}_h \notin \mathcal{X}_{\delta'}} \\ &+ \sum_{h=0}^{K'-1} \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left(\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \right) \mathbf{1}_{\mathbf{x}_h \in \mathcal{X}_{\delta'}} \\ &+ \sum_{h=K'}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left(\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \right) \mathbf{1}_{\mathbf{x}_h \in \mathcal{X}_{\delta'}} =: \mathcal{K}_{1,1}^k + \mathcal{K}_{1,2}^k + \mathcal{K}_{1,3}^k. \end{aligned}$$

For $\mathcal{K}_{1,1}^k$, since $\mathbf{x}_h \in \mathcal{X}$ and $\mathbf{x}_h \rightarrow \mathbf{x}^*$ as $h \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely (cf. Assumption 5), we know for any run of the sequence $\{\mathbf{x}_h\}$, there exist a (potentially random) $\tilde{h} < \infty$ and a constant $\Upsilon_2(\tilde{h}) > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{K}_{1,1}^k\| &= \left\| \sum_{h=0}^{\tilde{h}} \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left(\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \right) \mathbf{1}_{\mathbf{x}_h \notin \mathcal{X}_{\delta'}} \right\| \\ &\leq \sum_{h=0}^{\tilde{h}} \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left\| \widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \right\| \mathbf{1}_{\mathbf{x}_h \notin \mathcal{X}_{\delta'}} \\ &= \sum_{h=0}^{\tilde{h}} \prod_{l=h+1}^{\tilde{h}} (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \left\| \widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \right\| \mathbf{1}_{\mathbf{x}_h \notin \mathcal{X}_{\delta'}} \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \end{aligned}$$

$$\stackrel{\text{(G.13)}}{\leq} \Upsilon_2(\bar{h}) \exp\left(-\frac{\iota_2 k^{1-p_2}}{1-p_2}\right).$$

This implies that

$$P\left(\bigcap_{M=0}^{\infty} \bigcap_{K=0}^{\infty} \mathcal{A}_{M,K}\right) := P\left(\bigcap_{M=0}^{\infty} \bigcap_{K=0}^{\infty} \bigcup_{k \geq K} \{k \|\mathcal{K}_{1,1}^k\| \geq M\}\right) = 0.$$

Since $\mathcal{A}_{M+1,K+1} \subseteq \mathcal{A}_{M,K}$, we have $\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty, K \rightarrow \infty} P(\mathcal{A}_{M,K}) = 0$. Thus, for any $\epsilon > 0$ there exist $M(\epsilon)$ and $K(\epsilon)$ such that for any $k \geq K(\epsilon)$, $P(k \|\mathcal{K}_{1,1}^k\| \geq M(\epsilon)) \leq \epsilon$. This means that $\|\mathcal{K}_{1,1}^k\| = O_p(1/k)$. Following the same analysis, we also obtain $\|\mathcal{K}_{1,2}^k\| = O_p(1/k)$. For $\mathcal{K}_{1,3}^k$, we apply the martingale difference property (noting that $\mathbf{1}_{\mathbf{x}_h \in \mathcal{X}_{\delta'}}$ is \mathcal{F}_{h-1} -measurable) and the bounded second moment condition, and obtain

$$\mathbb{E}[\|\mathcal{K}_{1,3}^k\|^2] \leq O\left(\sum_{h=K'}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l)^2 \beta_h^2\right) \leq O\left(\sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l)^2 \beta_h^2\right) = O(\beta_k),$$

where the last equality is due to Lemma 9. Combining the results of $\mathcal{K}_{1,1}^k$, $\mathcal{K}_{1,2}^k$, $\mathcal{K}_{1,3}^k$, we have

$$\|\mathcal{K}_1^k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \leq \|\mathcal{K}_1^k\|^2 = O_p(\beta_k). \quad (\text{G.18})$$

• For \mathcal{K}_2^k , we use $p_4 > 0.5p_3$, apply Lemmas 11 and 9, and have

$$\mathbb{E}[\|\mathcal{K}_2^k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k}] \leq O\left(\left\{\sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l) \beta_h (b_h + \tilde{b}_h^2/b_h)\right\}^2\right) = O(b_k^2 + \tilde{b}_k^4/b_k^2). \quad (\text{G.19})$$

• For \mathcal{K}_3^k , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{K}_3^k\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} &\leq \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l) \beta_h \|\nabla^2 f_h - \nabla^2 f^*\| \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\ &\leq \sum_{h=0}^{k_0-1} \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l) \beta_h \|\nabla^2 f_h - \nabla^2 f^*\| + \sum_{h=k_0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l) \beta_h \|\nabla^2 f_h - \nabla^2 f^*\| \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > h} =: \mathcal{K}_{3,1}^k + \mathcal{K}_{3,2}^k. \end{aligned}$$

By the same analysis as in $\mathcal{K}_{1,1}^k$, we know $\mathcal{K}_{3,1}^k = O_p(1/k)$. For $\mathcal{K}_{3,2}^k$, we apply the Lipschitz continuity condition and Lemmas 7 and 9, and have for some constants $\Upsilon_3 > 0$, $\Upsilon_4(k_0) > 0$, $\Upsilon_5(k_0) > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[(\mathcal{K}_{3,2}^k)^2] &\leq \Upsilon_3 \left(\sum_{h=k_0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l) \beta_h \{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{x}_h - \mathbf{x}^*\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > h}]\}^{1/2}\right)^2 \\ &\leq \Upsilon_4(k_0) \left(\sum_{h=k_0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l) \beta_h (\sqrt{\beta_h} + b_h^2)\right)^2 \leq \Upsilon_5(k_0) (\beta_k + b_k^4). \end{aligned}$$

Combining the above two displays, we have

$$\|\mathcal{K}_3^k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} = O_p(\beta_k + b_k^4). \quad (\text{G.20})$$

• For \mathcal{K}_4^k , we apply (G.3) and follow the same analysis as \mathcal{J}_3^k . We obtain for some constant $\Upsilon_6 > 0$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{K}_4^k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} &\leq \Upsilon_6 \left\{\sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l) \beta_h \|\lambda_h - \lambda^*\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k}\right\}^2 \\ &\leq \Upsilon_6 \left\{\left(\sum_{h=0}^{k_0-1} + \sum_{h=k_0}^k\right) \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1-\beta_l) \beta_h \|\lambda_h - \lambda^*\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > h}\right\}^2 = O_p(\beta_k + b_k^4). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G.21})$$

Combining (G.18), (G.19), (G.20), (G.21), ignoring higher-order error terms, and establishing the same bounds for \mathcal{J}_5^k , \mathcal{J}_6^k , \mathcal{J}_7^k , we obtain

$$\|\bar{B}_k - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}^*\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} = O_p(\beta_k + b_k^2 + \tilde{b}_k^4/b_k^2).$$

Following the same analysis, we can derive the same bound for $\|\bar{G}_k - G^*\|^2$. Plugging into (G.17), we complete the proof.

G.7. Proof of Theorem 2

To streamline the proof, we first present a generic lemma, which is proved in Appendix G.8. We will apply this lemma to various terms that appear throughout the proof.

LEMMA 16. *Consider a sequence of random variables $\{X_k\}_{k=0}^\infty$ and a sequence of events $\{\mathcal{A}_k\}_{k=0}^\infty$. Let $\tau_{k_0} = \inf\{k \geq k_0 : \mathcal{A}_k \text{ happens}\}$ be the first index k after k_0 such that \mathcal{A}_k happens. Suppose that for each realization of the sequence, there exists a (potentially random) $\bar{k}_0 < \infty$ such that $\tau_{\bar{k}_0} = \infty$ (in other words, \mathcal{A}_k will finally not happen almost surely). Also, for the sequence $\alpha_k = \iota_1 / (k + 1)^{p_1}$ with $p_1 \in (0, 1]$, suppose there exists a deterministic $\bar{k}_0 > 0$ such that for any fixed $k_0 \geq \bar{k}_0$, $X_k \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k})$. Then, for any constant $\zeta > 0$ satisfying $\zeta \iota_1 > 0.5$ when $p_1 = 1$, we have*

$$\sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k}).$$

We first decompose the primal-dual error term of Algorithm 1. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}_{k+1} &= \mathbf{z}_k - \bar{\alpha}_k \tilde{W}_k^{-1} \bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k = \mathbf{z}_k - \zeta \alpha_k \tilde{W}_k^{-1} \bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - (\bar{\alpha}_k - \zeta \alpha_k) \tilde{W}_k^{-1} \bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k \\ &= (1 - \zeta \alpha_k) \mathbf{z}_k - \zeta \alpha_k \tilde{W}_k^{-1} (\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \tilde{W}_k \mathbf{z}_k) - \zeta \alpha_k \tilde{W}_k^{-1} (\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k) - (\bar{\alpha}_k - \zeta \alpha_k) \tilde{W}_k^{-1} \bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k \\ &= (1 - \zeta \alpha_k) \mathbf{z}_k - \zeta \alpha_k \tilde{W}_k^{-1} (\nabla \mathcal{L}_k - W^* \mathbf{z}_k) - \zeta \alpha_k \tilde{W}_k^{-1} (W^* - \tilde{W}_k) \mathbf{z}_k - \zeta \alpha_k (W^*)^{-1} (\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k) \\ &\quad - \zeta \alpha_k (\tilde{W}_k^{-1} - (W^*)^{-1}) (\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k) - (\bar{\alpha}_k - \zeta \alpha_k) \tilde{W}_k^{-1} \bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k \\ &= \prod_{i=0}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_i) \mathbf{z}_0 - \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \{ \tilde{W}_i^{-1} (\nabla \mathcal{L}_i - W^* \mathbf{z}_i) + \tilde{W}_i^{-1} (W^* - \tilde{W}_i) \mathbf{z}_i \} \\ &\quad - \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \left\{ (\tilde{W}_i^{-1} - (W^*)^{-1}) (\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla \mathcal{L}_i) + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_i - \zeta \alpha_i}{\zeta \alpha_i} \tilde{W}_i^{-1} \bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_i \right\} \\ &\quad - \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i (W^*)^{-1} (\bar{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla \mathcal{L}_i) =: C_1^k - C_2^k - C_3^k - C_4^k. \end{aligned}$$

In the following proof, we choose the (deterministic) constant ϵ to be sufficiently small such that, for each run of the algorithm, there exists a (potentially random) $\bar{k}_0 < \infty$ satisfying $\tau_{\bar{k}_0}(\epsilon) = \infty$, where $\tau_{k_0}(\epsilon)$ is defined in (25). This ϵ exists because, for each run of the algorithm:

- (a) $\|\mathbf{z}_k\| > \epsilon^2$ and $\|(\mathbf{x}_k, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k)\| > 1/\epsilon$ will finally not happen since (27) implies (23), and Lemma 5 shows that $\mathbf{z}_k \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely.
 - (b) $\|\tilde{W}_k^{-1}\| > 1/\epsilon$, $\delta_k^G \neq \mathbf{0}$, and $\delta_k^B \neq \mathbf{0}$ will finally not happen since (27) implies (20) and (24), and Lemmas 1 and 6 show that $\tilde{W}_k \rightarrow W^* = \nabla^2 \mathcal{L}^*$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely.
 - (c) $\|\nabla \mathcal{L}_k - \tilde{W}_k \mathbf{z}_k\| > 0.25\epsilon^2 \|\mathbf{z}_k\|$, $\|\nabla \mathcal{L}_k\| > \|\mathbf{z}_k\|/\epsilon$, and $\|\nabla \mathcal{L}_k - W^* \mathbf{z}_k\| > \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2/\epsilon$ will finally not happen since $\nabla^2 \mathcal{L}$ is Lipschitz continuous near $(\mathbf{x}^*, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*)$ by Assumption 1 and $\tilde{W}_k \rightarrow W^*$.
 - (d) $\nu_k / (\tau_k \kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) \neq \zeta$ will finally not happen by Assumption 7.
- For C_1^k , we follow (G.13), apply $\zeta \iota_1 > 0.5$ when $p_1 = 1$, and have $C_1^k = o(\sqrt{\alpha_k})$.
 - For C_2^k , we apply Lemmas 7 and 13, and have for $k \geq k_0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \|\tilde{W}_k^{-1} (\nabla \mathcal{L}_k - W^* \mathbf{z}_k) + \tilde{W}_k^{-1} (W^* - \tilde{W}_k) \mathbf{z}_k\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} &\stackrel{(25)}{\leq} \frac{1}{\epsilon^2} \|\mathbf{z}_k\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} + \frac{1}{\epsilon} \|\tilde{W}_k - W^*\| \|\mathbf{z}_k\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\ &\leq O_p(\beta_k + b_k^4) + O_p\left(\left\{\sqrt{\beta_k} + b_k + \tilde{b}_k^2/b_k\right\} \left\{\sqrt{\beta_k} + b_k^2\right\}\right) \\ &= O_p\left(\beta_k + \sqrt{\beta_k} b_k + b_k^3 + \sqrt{\beta_k} \tilde{b}_k^2/b_k + \tilde{b}_k^2 b_k\right). \end{aligned}$$

We note that

$$\begin{aligned} O_p\left(\beta_k + \sqrt{\beta_k} b_k + b_k^3 + \sqrt{\beta_k} \tilde{b}_k^2/b_k + \tilde{b}_k^2 b_k\right) &= o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k}) \\ &\iff \min\{p_2, 0.5p_2 + p_3, 3p_3, 0.5p_2 + 2p_4 - p_3, 2p_4 + p_3\} > 0.5p_1 \iff (27). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we apply Lemma 16 and have $C_2^k = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k})$.

- For C_3^k , we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left\| (\widetilde{W}_k^{-1} - (W^\star)^{-1})(\widetilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k) + \frac{\bar{\alpha}_k - \zeta \alpha_k}{\zeta \alpha_k} \widetilde{W}_k^{-1} \widetilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k \right\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\
& \stackrel{(25)}{\leq} \|\widetilde{W}_k^{-1} - (W^\star)^{-1}\| \|\widetilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} + \frac{\psi \alpha_k^{p-1}}{\epsilon \zeta} \|\widetilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\
& \stackrel{(25)}{\leq} \frac{\|(W^\star)^{-1}\| \|\widetilde{W}_k - W^\star\| \|\widetilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} + \frac{\psi \alpha_k^{p-1}}{\epsilon \zeta} \left\{ \|\widetilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_k - \nabla \mathcal{L}_k\| + \frac{\|\mathbf{z}_k\|}{\epsilon} \right\} \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k}}{\epsilon} \\
& = O_p \left(\left\{ \sqrt{\beta_k} + b_k + \widetilde{b}_k^2/b_k \right\} \left\{ \sqrt{\beta_k} + b_k^2 \right\} \right) + O_p \left(\alpha_k^{p-1} \left(\sqrt{\beta_k} + b_k^2 \right) \right) \\
& = O_p \left(\beta_k + \sqrt{\beta_k} b_k + b_k^3 + \sqrt{\beta_k} \widetilde{b}_k^2/b_k + \widetilde{b}_k^2 b_k + \alpha_k^{p-1} \sqrt{\beta_k} + \alpha_k^{p-1} b_k^2 \right).
\end{aligned}$$

We note that

$$\begin{aligned}
& O_p \left(\beta_k + \sqrt{\beta_k} b_k + b_k^3 + \sqrt{\beta_k} \widetilde{b}_k^2/b_k + \widetilde{b}_k^2 b_k + \alpha_k^{p-1} \sqrt{\beta_k} + \alpha_k^{p-1} b_k^2 \right) = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k}) \\
& \iff \min\{p_2, 0.5p_2 + p_3, 3p_3, 0.5p_2 + 2p_4 - p_3, 2p_4 + p_3, (p-1)p_1 + 0.5p_2, (p-1)p_1 + 2p_3\} > 0.5p_1 \\
& \iff (27).
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we apply Lemma 16 again and have $C_3^k = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k})$.

- For C_4^k , let us define $\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}; \xi) := \widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}; \xi) + \widehat{\nabla} c(\mathbf{x})^T \boldsymbol{\lambda}$. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
C_4^k &= \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i (W^\star)^{-1} (\widetilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla \mathcal{L}_i) = \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i (W^\star)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \widetilde{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}_i - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}_i \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \\
& \stackrel{(G.9)}{=} \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \cdot \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h}^i (1 - \beta_l) (W^\star)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_{h-1}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i) - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \\
& \quad + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \cdot \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^\star)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i; \xi_h) - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \\
& = \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \cdot \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h}^i (1 - \beta_l) (W^\star)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_{h-1}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i) - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_i) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \\
& \quad + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \cdot \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^\star)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} (\widehat{\nabla} c_h - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} c_h | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}])^T (\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i - \boldsymbol{\lambda}^\star) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \\
& \quad + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \cdot \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^\star)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} (\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} c_h | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] - G_h)^T (\boldsymbol{\lambda}_i - \boldsymbol{\lambda}^\star) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \\
& \quad + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \cdot \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^\star)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^\star; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^\star) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \\
& \quad + \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \cdot \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^\star)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^\star; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^\star; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \\
& =: C_{4,1}^k + C_{4,2}^k + C_{4,3}^k + C_{4,4}^k + C_{4,5}^k.
\end{aligned}$$

- For $C_{4,1}^k$, we know from Lemma 16 that it suffices to show

$$\sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h}^k (1 - \beta_l) (W^\star)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_{h-1}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k) - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}_k) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k}).$$

Since $\|\boldsymbol{\lambda}_k\| \leq 1/\epsilon$ when $\tau_{k_0} > k$, we apply Lemma 16 again and know that the above display is implied by

$$(\|\nabla f_{k-1} - \nabla f_k\| + \|G_{k-1} - G_k\|) \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} = o_p(\beta_k \sqrt{\alpha_k}).$$

By the Lipschitz continuity of ∇f and G , we know for $k \geq k_0 + 1$ that

$$\begin{aligned} & (\|\nabla f_{k-1} - \nabla f_k\| + \|G_{k-1} - G_k\|) \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \leq (\kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) \|\mathbf{x}_{k-1} - \mathbf{x}_k\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k-1} \\ & \leq (\kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) \bar{\alpha}_{k-1} \|\tilde{\Delta} \mathbf{x}_{k-1}\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k-1} \stackrel{(25)}{\leq} \frac{1}{\epsilon} (\kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) (\zeta \alpha_{k-1} + \psi \alpha_{k-1}^p) \|\tilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_{k-1}\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k-1} \\ & \leq \frac{1}{\epsilon} (\kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) (\zeta \alpha_{k-1} + \psi \alpha_{k-1}^p) (\|\tilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_{k-1} - \nabla \mathcal{L}_{k-1}\| + \|\nabla \mathcal{L}_{k-1}\|) \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k-1} \\ & \stackrel{(25)}{\leq} \frac{1}{\epsilon} (\kappa_{\nabla f} + \kappa_{\nabla c}) (\zeta \alpha_{k-1} + \psi \alpha_{k-1}^p) \left(\|\tilde{\nabla} \mathcal{L}_{k-1} - \nabla \mathcal{L}_{k-1}\| + \frac{\|\mathbf{z}_{k-1}\|}{\epsilon} \right) \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k-1} \\ & = O_p \left(\alpha_k \left(\sqrt{\beta_k} + b_k^2 \right) \right), \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality is due to Lemma 7. We note that

$$O_p \left(\alpha_k \left(\sqrt{\beta_k} + b_k^2 \right) \right) = o_p(\beta_k \sqrt{\alpha_k}) \iff \min\{p_1 + 0.5p_2, p_1 + 2p_3\} > p_2 + 0.5p_1 \iff (27).$$

Thus, we obtain $C_{4,1}^k = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k})$.

•• For $C_{4,2}^k$, we still apply Lemma 16. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^*)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} (\widehat{\nabla} c_h - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} c_h | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}])^T (\lambda_k - \lambda^*) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\ & \leq \left\| \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^*)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \widehat{\nabla} c_h - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} c_h | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} + \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\ & = O_p(\beta_k + b_k^4) \stackrel{(27)}{=} o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k}), \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality from the last is due to (G.10) and Lemma 7. Thus, Lemma 16 suggests that $C_{4,2}^k = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k})$.

•• For $C_{4,3}^k$, we have a similar derivation. In particular, we note that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^*)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} (\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} c_h | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] - G_h)^T (\lambda_k - \lambda^*) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\ & \leq \left\| \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^*)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla} c_h | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] - G_h \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\| \|\lambda_k - \lambda^*\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} \\ & = O_p(b_k^2 (\sqrt{\beta_k} + b_k^2)) \stackrel{(27)}{=} o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k}), \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality from the last is due to Lemmas 11 and 7 and (G.11). Thus, Lemma 16 suggests that $C_{4,3}^k = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k})$.

•• For $C_{4,4}^k$, we apply Lemma 11 and have

$$\left\| \sum_{h=0}^k \prod_{l=h+1}^k (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^*)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \lambda^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] - \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \lambda^*) \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \right\| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} > k} = O(b_k^2) \stackrel{(27)}{=} o(\sqrt{\alpha_k}).$$

Thus, Lemma 16 suggests that $C_{4,4}^k = o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k})$.

•• For $C_{4,5}^k$, we aim to show

$$1/\sqrt{\zeta \alpha_k} \cdot C_{4,5}^k \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \omega \cdot (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1}). \quad (\text{G.22})$$

We have

$$C_{4,5}^k = \sum_{i=0}^k \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^*)^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \lambda^*; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \lambda^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sum_{h=0}^k \sum_{i=h}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h (W^*)^{-1} \left(\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \right) \\
&=: \sum_{h=0}^k a_{h,k} \cdot \boldsymbol{\phi}_h. \tag{G.23}
\end{aligned}$$

We claim that $\mathbb{E}[\boldsymbol{\phi}_h \boldsymbol{\phi}_h^T | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \rightarrow (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1}$ as $h \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. In fact, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} \left[(\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}]) (\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}])^T | \mathcal{F}_{h-1} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1} \right] - \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}]^T.
\end{aligned}$$

Since $\mathbb{E}[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \rightarrow \nabla_x \mathcal{L}^* = \mathbf{0}$ as $h \rightarrow \infty$ by Lemma 11, we only consider the first term. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) | \mathcal{F}_{h-1} \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E} \left[(\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) + \widehat{\nabla}^T c(\mathbf{x}_h) \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*) (\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_h; \xi_h) + \widehat{\nabla}^T c(\mathbf{x}_h) \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*)^T | \mathcal{F}_{h-1} \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{4b_h^2} \mathbb{E} \left[\Delta_h^{-1} \left\{ \delta \left(F(\mathbf{x}_h \pm b_h \Delta_h; \xi_h) + c^T(\mathbf{x}_h \pm b_h \Delta_h) \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* \right) \right\}^2 \Delta_h^{-T} | \mathcal{F}_{h-1} \right] \\
&= \frac{1}{4b_h^2} \mathbb{E} \left[\Delta_h^{-1} \Delta_h^T \int_{-b_h}^{b_h} \int_{-b_h}^{b_h} \nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) \nabla_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) ds_1 ds_2 \Delta_h \Delta_h^{-T} | \mathcal{F}_{h-1} \right], \tag{G.24}
\end{aligned}$$

where in the second equality, we follow the definition in (8) and define

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta \left(F(\mathbf{x}_h \pm b_h \Delta_h; \xi_h) + c^T(\mathbf{x}_h \pm b_h \Delta_h) \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* \right) &:= \left(F(\mathbf{x}_h + b_h \Delta_h; \xi_h) + c^T(\mathbf{x}_h + b_h \Delta_h) \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* \right) \\
&\quad - \left(F(\mathbf{x}_h - b_h \Delta_h; \xi_h) + c^T(\mathbf{x}_h - b_h \Delta_h) \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* \right).
\end{aligned}$$

For (G.24), we first condition on both \mathbf{x}_h and Δ_h , and focus on the integrand. For each run of the algorithm, we consider h to be sufficiently large (with a potentially random threshold index) such that $\mathbf{x}_h \in \{\mathbf{x} : \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*\| \leq \delta'\}$, where $\delta' \in (0, \delta)$ is chosen to ensure that $\mathbf{x} + s\Delta \in \{\mathbf{x} : \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}^*\| \leq \delta\}$ for any $s \in [-b_h, b_h]$ and $\Delta \sim \mathcal{P}_\Delta$. For the above \mathbf{x}_h and any $-b_h \leq s_1, s_2 \leq b_h$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
&\mathbb{E} \left[\nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) \nabla_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi_h) | \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] - \mathbb{E} \left[\nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi) \nabla_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*; \xi) \right] \\
&= \mathbb{E} \left[\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h; \xi_h) \nabla^T F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h; \xi_h) - \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \nabla^T F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) | \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] \\
&\quad + \nabla f(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h) (\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*)^T G(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h) - \nabla f^*(\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*)^T G^* \\
&\quad + G^T(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h) \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* \nabla^T f(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h) - (G^*)^T \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* \nabla^T f^* \\
&\quad + G^T(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h) \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* (\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*)^T G(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h) - (G^*)^T \boldsymbol{\lambda}^* (\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*)^T G^*. \tag{G.25}
\end{aligned}$$

For the first term in (G.25), we can further bound it as

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left\| \mathbb{E} \left[\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h; \xi_h) \nabla^T F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h; \xi_h) - \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \nabla^T F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) | \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] \right\| \\
&\leq \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h; \xi_h) - \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\| \cdot \left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h; \xi_h) - \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\| | \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h; \xi_h) - \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\| \cdot \left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\| | \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] \\
&\quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h; \xi_h) - \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\| \cdot \left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\| | \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] \\
&\leq \prod_{q=1}^2 \left\{ \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_q \Delta_h; \xi_h) - \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\|^2 | \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] \right\}^{1/2} \\
&\quad + \left\{ \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\|^2 \right] \right\}^{1/2} \cdot \sum_{q=1}^2 \left\{ \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_q \Delta_h; \xi_h) - \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\|^2 | \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] \right\}^{1/2}.
\end{aligned}$$

Note from Assumptions 6 and 3 that for $q = 1, 2$,

$$\mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_q \Delta_h; \xi_h) - \nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi_h) \right\|^2 | \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \int_0^1 \nabla^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_q \Delta_h + t(\mathbf{x}_h + s_q \Delta_h - \mathbf{x}^*); \xi_h) (\mathbf{x}_h + s_q \Delta_h - \mathbf{x}^*) dt \right\|^2 \mid \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] \\
 &\leq \int_0^1 \mathbb{E} [\|\nabla^2 F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_q \Delta_h + t(\mathbf{x}_h + s_q \Delta_h - \mathbf{x}^*); \xi_h)\|^2 \mid \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h] dt \cdot \|\mathbf{x}_h + s_q \Delta_h - \mathbf{x}^*\|^2 \\
 &= O(\|\mathbf{x}_h - \mathbf{x}^*\|^2 + b_h^2) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } h \rightarrow \infty.
 \end{aligned}$$

The above two displays imply almost surely,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \max_{-b_h \leq s_1, s_2 \leq b_h} \left\{ \mathbb{E} \left[\nabla F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_1 \Delta_h; \xi_h) \nabla^T F(\mathbf{x}_h + s_2 \Delta_h; \xi_h) \mid \mathbf{x}_h, \Delta_h \right] \right. \\
 \left. - \mathbb{E} [\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi) \nabla^T F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)] \right\} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } h \rightarrow \infty.
 \end{aligned}$$

For the second, third, and fourth terms in (G.25), it is trivial to verify that they achieve the same almost sure convergence as the above display, due to the Lipschitz continuity of ∇f and G and the fact that $|s_1|, |s_2| \leq b_h \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore, we combine (G.24) and (G.25) and obtain almost surely,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \lambda^*; \xi_h) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_h, \lambda^*; \xi_h) \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1} \right] \\
 &\quad \rightarrow \mathbb{E} \left[\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T \mathbb{E} \left[\nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*; \xi) \nabla_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*; \xi) \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1} \right] \Delta \Delta^{-T} \right] \\
 &\quad = \mathbb{E} \left[\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T \text{Cov} \left(\nabla_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}^*, \lambda^*; \xi) \right) \Delta \Delta^{-T} \right] \\
 &\quad = \mathbb{E} \left[\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T \text{Cov} \left(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi) \right) \Delta \Delta^{-T} \right]. \tag{G.26}
 \end{aligned}$$

This, together with (G.24) and the definition of ϕ_h in (G.23), implies $\mathbb{E}[\phi_h \phi_h^T \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \rightarrow (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1}$ as $h \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. With this result, we then analyze the conditional variance process. We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{h=0}^k a_{h,k}^2 \mathbb{E}[\phi_h \phi_h^T \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \\
 &= \frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{h=0}^k \sum_{i=h}^k \sum_{i'=h}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \prod_{j'=i'+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'}) \zeta \alpha_{i'} \prod_{l'=h+1}^{i'} (1 - \beta_{l'}) \beta_h \mathbb{E}[\phi_h \phi_h^T \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \\
 &= \frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \sum_{i'=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \prod_{j'=i'+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'}) \zeta \alpha_{i'} \sum_{h=0}^{\min\{i, i'\}} \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \prod_{l'=h+1}^{i'} (1 - \beta_{l'}) \beta_h^2 \mathbb{E}[\phi_h \phi_h^T \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \\
 &= \frac{2}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \sum_{i'=0}^i \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \prod_{j'=i'+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'}) \zeta \alpha_{i'} \sum_{h=0}^{i'} \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \prod_{l'=h+1}^{i'} (1 - \beta_{l'}) \beta_h^2 \mathbb{E}[\phi_h \phi_h^T \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j)^2 \zeta^2 \alpha_i^2 \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l)^2 \beta_h^2 \mathbb{E}[\phi_h \phi_h^T \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \\
 &= \frac{2}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j)^2 \zeta \alpha_i \sum_{i'=0}^i \prod_{j'=i'+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'}) (1 - \beta_{j'}) \zeta \alpha_{i'} \sum_{h=0}^{i'} \prod_{l'=h+1}^{i'} (1 - \beta_{l'})^2 \beta_h^2 \mathbb{E}[\phi_h \phi_h^T \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j)^2 \zeta^2 \alpha_i^2 \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l)^2 \beta_h^2 \mathbb{E}[\phi_h \phi_h^T \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1}].
 \end{aligned}$$

We apply Lemma 9 and note that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\beta_i} \sum_{h=0}^i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l)^2 \beta_h^2 \mathbb{E}[\phi_h \phi_h^T \mid \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] &= \frac{1}{2} (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1}, \\
 \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_i} \sum_{i'=0}^i \prod_{j'=i'+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'}) (1 - \beta_{j'}) \zeta \alpha_{i'} \beta_{i'} &= 1, \\
 \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j)^2 \zeta^2 \alpha_i^2 &= \omega := \begin{cases} 0.5, & \text{if } p_1 \in (0, 1), \\ \frac{\zeta t_1}{2\zeta t_1 - 1}, & \text{if } p_1 = 1, \end{cases}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j)^2 \zeta^2 \alpha_i^2 \beta_i = 0.$$

Combining the above two displays, we obtain almost surely,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_k} \sum_{h=0}^k a_{h,k}^2 \mathbb{E}[\boldsymbol{\phi}_h \boldsymbol{\phi}_h^T | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] = \boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot (\mathbf{W}^*)^{-1} \boldsymbol{\Omega}^* (\mathbf{W}^*)^{-1}. \quad (\text{G.27})$$

Next, we verify the Lindeberg condition. We aim to show that for any $\epsilon > 0$,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\alpha_k} \sum_{h=0}^k a_{h,k}^2 \mathbb{E}[\|\boldsymbol{\phi}_h\|^2 \mathbf{1}_{\|a_{h,k} \boldsymbol{\phi}_h\| \geq \epsilon \sqrt{\alpha_k}} | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] \leq \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\epsilon \alpha_k^{1.5}} \sum_{h=0}^k a_{h,k}^3 \mathbb{E}[\|\boldsymbol{\phi}_h\|^3 | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}] = 0. \quad (\text{G.28})$$

Since $r \geq 3$ in (27), we know from (F.7) that $\mathbb{E}[\|\boldsymbol{\phi}_h\|^3 | \mathcal{F}_{h-1}]$ is uniformly bounded. Thus, it suffices to show $\sum_{h=0}^k a_{h,k}^3 = o(\alpha_k^{1.5})$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{h=0}^k a_{h,k}^3 &= \sum_{h=0}^k \sum_{i=h}^k \sum_{i'=h}^k \sum_{i''=h}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \beta_h \prod_{j'=i'+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'}) \zeta \alpha_{i'} \prod_{l'=h+1}^{i'} (1 - \beta_{l'}) \beta_h \\ &\quad \prod_{j''=i''+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j''}) \zeta \alpha_{i''} \prod_{l''=h+1}^{i''} (1 - \beta_{l''}) \beta_h \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^k \sum_{i'=0}^k \sum_{i''=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \prod_{j'=i'+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'}) \zeta \alpha_{i'} \prod_{j''=i''+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j''}) \zeta \alpha_{i''} \\ &\quad \sum_{h=0}^{\min\{i, i', i''\}} \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \prod_{l'=h+1}^{i'} (1 - \beta_{l'}) \prod_{l''=h+1}^{i''} (1 - \beta_{l''}) \beta_h^3 \\ &\leq 6 \sum_{i=0}^k \sum_{i'=0}^i \sum_{i''=0}^{i'} \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \zeta \alpha_i \prod_{j'=i'+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'}) \zeta \alpha_{i'} \prod_{j''=i''+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j''}) \zeta \alpha_{i''} \\ &\quad \sum_{h=0}^{i''} \prod_{l=h+1}^i (1 - \beta_l) \prod_{l'=h+1}^{i'} (1 - \beta_{l'}) \prod_{l''=h+1}^{i''} (1 - \beta_{l''}) \beta_h^3 \quad (i \geq i' \geq i'') \\ &= 6 \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j)^3 \zeta \alpha_i \sum_{i'=0}^i \prod_{j'=i'+1}^i (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'})^2 (1 - \beta_{j'}) \zeta \alpha_{i'} \\ &\quad \sum_{i''=0}^{i'} \prod_{j''=i''+1}^{i'} (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j''}) (1 - \beta_{j''})^2 \zeta \alpha_{i''} \sum_{h=0}^{i''} \prod_{l''=h+1}^{i''} (1 - \beta_{l''})^3 \beta_h^3. \end{aligned}$$

We apply Lemma 9 and (Na and Mahoney 2025, Lemma B.3(b)) and note that

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{i'' \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\beta_{i''}^2} \sum_{h=0}^{i''} \prod_{l''=h+1}^{i''} (1 - \beta_{l''})^3 \beta_h^3 &= \frac{1}{3}, \\ \lim_{i' \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{\zeta \alpha_{i'} \beta_{i'}} \sum_{i''=0}^{i'} \prod_{j''=i''+1}^{i'} (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j''}) (1 - \beta_{j''})^2 \zeta \alpha_{i''} \beta_{i''}^2 &= \frac{1}{2}, \\ \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{(\zeta \alpha_i)^2} \sum_{i'=0}^i \prod_{j'=i'+1}^i (1 - \zeta \alpha_{j'})^2 (1 - \beta_{j'}) (\zeta \alpha_{i'})^2 \beta_{i'} &= 1, \\ \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{(\zeta \alpha_k)^{1.5}} \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j)^3 (\zeta \alpha_i)^3 &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

where the last equality applies $\zeta_{l_1} > 0.5$ when $p_1 = 1$. Thus, we have $\sum_{h=0}^k a_{h,k}^3 = o(\alpha_k^{1.5})$. By the central limit theorem of martingale arrays (Hall and Heyde 2014, Corollary 3.1), the results (G.27) and (G.28) lead to (G.22).

Finally, we combine the result of $C_{4,5}^k$ in (G.22) with all the results of $C_1^k, C_2^k, C_3^k, C_{4,1}^k, C_{4,2}^k, C_{4,3}^k, C_{4,4}^k$, for which we have shown that each is of order $o_p(\sqrt{\alpha_k})$. We obtain

$$1/\sqrt{\zeta\alpha_k} \cdot (\mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}^*, \lambda_k - \lambda^*) \xrightarrow{d} \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \omega \cdot (W^*)^{-1} \Omega^* (W^*)^{-1}).$$

Noting that $\bar{\alpha}_k/(\zeta\alpha_k) \rightarrow 1$ almost surely and applying Slutsky's theorem, we complete the proof.

G.8. Proof of Lemma 16

We aim to show that for any $\epsilon, \delta > 0$, there exists $K = K(\epsilon, \delta) > 0$ such that for any $k \geq K(\epsilon, \delta)$,

$$P\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \right| \geq \epsilon\right) \leq \delta. \tag{G.29}$$

For the above fixed $\epsilon, \delta > 0$, we know from $P(\cup_{k_0=0}^\infty \{\tau_{k_0} = \infty\}) = 1$ that

$$P\left(\bigcap_{k_0=0}^\infty \mathcal{B}_{k_0}\right) := P\left(\bigcap_{k_0=0}^\infty \bigcup_{k'_0 \geq k_0+1} \bigcup_{k \geq k'_0} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \sum_{i=k'_0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k |(1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} \leq i} \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3} \right\}\right) = 0.$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{B}_{k_0+1} &= \bigcup_{k'_0 \geq k_0+1} \bigcup_{k \geq k'_0} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \sum_{i=k'_0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k |(1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0+1} \leq i} \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3} \right\} \\ &\subseteq \bigcup_{k'_0 \geq k_0+1} \bigcup_{k \geq k'_0} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \sum_{i=k'_0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k |(1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} \leq i} \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3} \right\} \quad (\text{since } \tau_{k_0+1} \geq \tau_{k_0}) \\ &\subseteq \bigcup_{k'_0 \geq k_0} \bigcup_{k \geq k'_0} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \sum_{i=k'_0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k |(1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0} \leq i} \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3} \right\} = \mathcal{B}_{k_0}, \end{aligned}$$

the above two displays imply that $\lim_{k_0 \rightarrow \infty} P(\mathcal{B}_{k_0}) = 0$. Thus, there exists $k_0(\delta) \geq \bar{k}_0$ such that for any $k \geq k_0(\delta)$,

$$\begin{aligned} &P\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=k_0(\delta)}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0(\delta)} \leq i} \right| \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3}\right) \\ &\leq P\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \sum_{i=k_0(\delta)}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k |(1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0(\delta)} \leq i} \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3}\right) \\ &\leq P\left(\bigcup_{k \geq k_0(\delta)} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \sum_{i=k_0(\delta)}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k |(1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i| \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0(\delta)} \leq i} \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3} \right\}\right) \leq P(\mathcal{B}_{k_0(\delta)}) \leq \frac{\delta}{3}. \end{aligned} \tag{G.30}$$

For the above $k_0(\delta)$ fixed, we apply Lemma 9 and have

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \sum_{i=k_0(\delta)}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0(\delta)} > i} = o_p\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \sum_{i=k_0(\delta)}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i^{1.5}\right) = o_p(1).$$

Thus, there exists $K^1 = K^1(\epsilon, \delta) \geq k_0(\delta)$ such that for any $k \geq K^1(\epsilon, \delta)$,

$$P\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=k_0(\delta)}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0(\delta)} > i} \right| \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3}\right) \leq \frac{\delta}{3}. \tag{G.31}$$

Finally, we note that with probability 1,

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=0}^{k_0(\delta)-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \right| \leq \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \sum_{i=0}^{k_0(\delta)-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k_0(\delta)-1} |(1 - \zeta\alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i| \cdot \prod_{j=k_0(\delta)}^k |1 - \zeta\alpha_j|$$

$$\stackrel{(G.13)}{\longrightarrow} 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow \infty.$$

This implies that

$$P\left(\bigcap_{k \geq k_0(\delta)} C_k\right) := P\left(\bigcap_{k \geq k_0(\delta)} \bigcup_{k' \geq k} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=0}^{k_0(\delta)-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^{k'} (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \right| \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3} \right\}\right) = 0.$$

Since $C_{k+1} \subseteq C_k$, we have $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} P(C_k) = 0$. Thus, there exists $K^2(\epsilon, \delta) \geq k_0(\delta)$ such that for any $k \geq K^2(\epsilon, \delta)$,

$$P\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=0}^{k_0(\delta)-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \right| \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3}\right) \leq P(C_k) \leq \frac{\delta}{3}. \quad (G.32)$$

Combining (G.30), (G.31), (G.32), and letting $K(\epsilon, \delta) := \max\{K^1(\epsilon, \delta), K^2(\epsilon, \delta)\}$, we have $\forall k \geq K(\epsilon, \delta)$,

$$\begin{aligned} & P\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=0}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \right| \geq \epsilon\right) \\ & \leq P\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=0}^{k_0(\delta)-1} \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \right| \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3}\right) + P\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=k_0(\delta)}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0(\delta)} > i} \right| \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3}\right) \\ & \quad + P\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_k}} \left| \sum_{i=k_0(\delta)}^k \prod_{j=i+1}^k (1 - \zeta \alpha_j) \alpha_i X_i \mathbf{1}_{\tau_{k_0(\delta)} \leq i} \right| \geq \frac{\epsilon}{3}\right) \leq \frac{\delta}{3} + \frac{\delta}{3} + \frac{\delta}{3} = \delta. \end{aligned}$$

This verifies (G.29) and completes the proof.

G.9. Proof of Proposition 1

By the definition of Σ^* , Σ_{op}^* and Ω^* , we note that

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma^* - \Sigma_{op}^* &= (W^*)^{-1} (\Omega^* - \text{diag}(\text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)), \mathbf{0})) (W^*)^{-1} \\ &= (W^*)^{-1} \text{diag}\left(\mathbb{E}\left[\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \Delta \Delta^{-T}\right] - \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)), \mathbf{0}\right) (W^*)^{-1} \\ &= (W^*)^{-1} \text{diag}\left(\mathbb{E}\left[\left(\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T - I\right) \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \left(\Delta \Delta^{-T} - I\right)\right], \mathbf{0}\right) (W^*)^{-1} \succeq \mathbf{0}, \end{aligned}$$

where the third equality is due to $\mathbb{E}[\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T] = \mathbb{E}[\Delta \Delta^{-T}] = I$ by Assumption 3. For the second part of the result, we follow the above result and have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Sigma^* - \Sigma_{op}^*\| &\geq \frac{1}{\|W^*\|^2} \left\| \text{diag}\left(\mathbb{E}\left[\left(\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T - I\right) \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \left(\Delta \Delta^{-T} - I\right)\right], \mathbf{0}\right) \right\| \\ &= \frac{1}{\|W^*\|^2} \left\| \mathbb{E}\left[\left(\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T - I\right) \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \left(\Delta \Delta^{-T} - I\right)\right] \right\| \\ &\geq \frac{\lambda_{\min}(\text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)))}{\|W^*\|^2} \left\| \mathbb{E}\left[\left(\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T - I\right) \left(\Delta \Delta^{-T} - I\right)\right] \right\| \\ &= \frac{\lambda_{\min}(\text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)))}{\|W^*\|^2} \left\| \mathbb{E}[\Delta^T \Delta \cdot \Delta^{-1} \Delta^{-T}] - I \right\| \\ &= \frac{\lambda_{\min}(\text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)))}{\|W^*\|^2} \cdot (d-1) \mathbb{E}[\Delta^2] \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{\Delta^2}\right] \quad (\text{by Assumption 3}). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we also have

$$\begin{aligned} \|\Sigma^* - \Sigma_{op}^*\| &\leq \|(W^*)^{-1}\|^2 \left\| \text{diag}\left(\mathbb{E}\left[\left(\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T - I\right) \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \left(\Delta \Delta^{-T} - I\right)\right], \mathbf{0}\right) \right\| \\ &= \|(W^*)^{-1}\|^2 \left\| \mathbb{E}\left[\left(\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T - I\right) \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \left(\Delta \Delta^{-T} - I\right)\right] \right\| \\ &\leq \|(W^*)^{-1}\|^2 \lambda_{\max}(\text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi))) \left\| \mathbb{E}\left[\left(\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T - I\right) \left(\Delta \Delta^{-T} - I\right)\right] \right\| \\ &= \|(W^*)^{-1}\|^2 \lambda_{\max}(\text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi))) \left\| \mathbb{E}[\Delta^T \Delta \cdot \Delta^{-1} \Delta^{-T}] - I \right\| \\ &= \|(W^*)^{-1}\|^2 \lambda_{\max}(\text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi))) \cdot (d-1) \mathbb{E}[\Delta^2] \mathbb{E}\left[\frac{1}{\Delta^2}\right]. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

G.10. Proof of Proposition 2

By Lemmas 1 and 6, we know $\tilde{W}_k \rightarrow W^*$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. Thus, it suffices to show

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{k+1} \sum_{t=0}^k \left(\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_t; \xi_t) + \widehat{\nabla}^T c(\mathbf{x}_t) \lambda_t \right) \left(\widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_t; \xi_t) + \widehat{\nabla}^T c(\mathbf{x}_t) \lambda_t \right)^T \\ & \quad \rightarrow \mathbb{E} \left[\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \Delta \Delta^{-T} \right] \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow \infty \text{ almost surely.} \end{aligned}$$

Recall from the proof of C_4^k in Appendix G.7 that we define $\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda_t; \xi_t) := \widehat{\nabla} F(\mathbf{x}_t; \xi_t) + \widehat{\nabla}^T c(\mathbf{x}_t) \lambda_t$. Since $r \geq 4$, we apply (F.7) and the strong law of large number for square integrable martingales (Duflo 1997, Theorem 1.3.15), and know that

$$\frac{1}{k+1} \sum_{t=0}^k \left(\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda_t; \xi_t) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda_t; \xi_t) - \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda_t; \xi_t) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda_t; \xi_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] \right) \rightarrow 0 \quad (\text{G.33})$$

as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. Furthermore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda_t; \xi_t) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda_t; \xi_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] - \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda^*; \xi_t) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda^*; \xi_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] \\ & = \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}^T c(\mathbf{x}_t) (\lambda_t - \lambda^*) \widehat{\nabla}^T f(\mathbf{x}_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla} f(\mathbf{x}_t) (\lambda_t - \lambda^*)^T \widehat{\nabla} c(\mathbf{x}_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] \\ & \quad + \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}^T c(\mathbf{x}_t) (\lambda_t - \lambda^*) (\lambda_t - \lambda^*)^T \widehat{\nabla} c(\mathbf{x}_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] \\ & = O(\|\lambda_t - \lambda^*\| + \|\lambda_t - \lambda^*\|^2) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } t \rightarrow \infty \text{ almost surely,} \end{aligned}$$

where the second equality is due to the boundedness of $\widehat{\nabla} f(\mathbf{x}_t)$ and $\widehat{\nabla} c(\mathbf{x}_t)$, which is as shown in (F.3). Therefore, the Stolz–Cesàro theorem suggests that

$$\frac{1}{k+1} \sum_{t=0}^k \left(\mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda_t; \xi_t) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda_t; \xi_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] - \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda^*; \xi_t) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda^*; \xi_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] \right) \rightarrow 0$$

as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. Finally, applying (G.26) and the Stolz–Cesàro theorem again, we obtain

$$\frac{1}{k+1} \sum_{t=0}^k \mathbb{E} \left[\widehat{\nabla}_x \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda^*; \xi_t) \widehat{\nabla}_x^T \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_t, \lambda^*; \xi_t) \mid \mathcal{F}_{t-1} \right] \rightarrow \mathbb{E} \left[\Delta^{-1} \Delta^T \text{Cov}(\nabla F(\mathbf{x}^*; \xi)) \Delta \Delta^{-T} \right]$$

as $k \rightarrow \infty$ almost surely. Combining the above two displays with (G.33), we complete the proof.